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Computationally Efficient Probabilistic Label Spreading via Algebraic Multigrid Methods

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1 Introduction

The advancement of neural networks over the past two decades has enabled machine learning methods to address an increasing range of complex tasks across diverse application domains. Many of these methods, particularly those based on supervised learning, rely on annotated datasets. Annotated datasets are collections of data that have been enriched with additional information, which is called a label, to provide context and meaning to the underlying context. These annotations serve as reference points for training and evaluating machine learning models, for example, in classification or regression problems [12]. As an example in image recognition in the task of classification, a dataset consists of images with labels indicating the presence of objects. With the help of this data, it is then possible to train a machine learning model to predict the contents of given images [16].

A drawback of the requirement for annotated data, is that a substantial amount is needed to train a model. Typically, humans label the data, a process that consumes a significant amount of time, rendering it both costly and inefficient, while unlabeled data is easier to obtain [11]. Here, the concept of label spreading comes into play, representing a semi-supervised learning method, which is already being applied in the field of classification [33, 11]. This technique enables the labeling of only a portion of the dataset, after which the information obtained from these labeled data points is shared across the entire dataset. This facilitates the derivation of labels for the unlabeled points using this shared information, thereby reducing the necessity for manual labeling.

A specific category of labels are probabilistic labels [21]. These are characterized by each instance in the dataset not having a single label but receiving a distribution over all possible labels. In crowdsourcing, for example, a probability for a label arises when multiple annotators label the same instance of the dataset and disagree. Similarly, in the field of medical diagnosis, probabilities for labels emerge as a result of a patient's examination, with the subsequent report indicating the likelihood of a particular illness. In most cases, probabilistic labels are more informative than deterministic labels because they provide information about how confident an instance can be assigned to a label [21]. One disadvantage of probabilistic labels in the context of crowdsourcing is that the process of labeling the data is significantly more time-consuming than that of labeling non-probabilistic datasets. This is due to the necessity of labeling each data point on multiple occasions. In [3], the label spreading method was expanded and adapted for a new application: probabilistic labels. In this approach, sharing information is considered as a crowdsourcing experiment, reducing the need for manual crowdsourcing

experiments in probabilistic labeling. Another advantageous aspect is the increased information available for each individual data point, which serves to minimize epistemic uncertainty and enhance the reliability and trustworthiness of data annotations.

The focus of this study is on the label spreading method, which is based on [33]. The idea is to utilize a classification function capable of categorizing both labeled and unlabeled data while satisfying certain consistency assumptions. This means that nearby points should have the same label and data points on the same structure should have the same label. The classification function is constructed using a graph-based approach, with data points acting as nodes and edges representing the similarity between pairs of data points. The construction involves solving a large linear system of equations, where the matrix is determined by the graph's adjacency matrix. Consequently, the size of this linear system scales with the number of data points in the dataset. Nowadays, maximizing available data is crucial, necessitating an efficient approach to solving this linear system.

A suitable method for solving large sparse and unstructured linear systems of equations are algebraic multigrid methods [30]. Algebraic multigrid methods are a hierarchical and purely matrix based approach. This implies that a given problem is solved on various levels, consisting of different subsets of variables. These subsets are determined solely based on the algebraic information contained in the given matrix, therefore no geometric background of the given system is required. The advantages of algebraic multigrid methods include their robustness and efficiency, which permit the solution of large systems of equations within acceptable computation times.

The objective of this master's thesis is to enhance the label spreading and the probabilistic label spreading method by integrating an algebraic multigrid solver. This integration enables the use of label spreading and probabilistic label spreading for large datasets, thereby ensuring computational efficiency. The results demonstrate that by using label spreading, it is possible to achieve high classification accuracies with limited per-hand labeled data points. Consequently, the need for manual labeling is reduced. Furthermore, it is demonstrated that probabilistic label spreading can be employed to achieve a rapid reduction in the difference between the true probabilistic labels and the estimated labels obtained by crowdsourcing through a limited number of crowdsourcing experiments. Furthermore, the efficiency of label spreading and probabilistic label spreading can be enhanced through the utilisation of an algebraic multigrid solver for the linear system of equations. This makes label spreading and probabilistic label spreading highly practical approaches, reducing the number of labeling processes and the number of human-conducted experiments while also ensuring computational efficiency.

The following procedure is presented in this thesis. In Chapter 2, the label spreading algorithm for classification problems is first introduced, including theoretical foundations. Chapter 3 introduces probabilistic labels and elucidates the potential for extending the label spreading method to apply to probabilistic labels. Methods to reduce the dimension of data are presented in Chapter 4, which are needed to make the label spreading method

applicable to high-dimensional data. Chapter 5 introduces iterative linear solvers for linear systems of equations, with a particular focus on algebraic multigrid methods. These are essential for the efficient solution of large sparse systems of equations, which arise in the label spreading and in the probabilistic label spreading algorithm. Subsequently, experiments are presented in Chapter 6 to demonstrate the efficiency of these solvers in facilitating fast label spreading. Additionally, experiments for probabilistic label spreading are discussed.

2 Label Spreading

This chapter provides an introduction to the topic of label spreading for classification problems, which belongs to the field of semi-supervised learning problems. First, the task of label spreading is defined, introduced by [33]. Based on [18, 4], some fundamentals of semi-supervised learning are provided. Following that, a brief overview of graph theory is offered according to [1, 5] to elucidate the relationship between label spreading and the heat equation. Subsequently, the task of label spreading is considered. Derived from [33] it is explained how a classification function can be constructed that satisfies certain assumptions of the semi-supervised learning problem and can predict labels for the unlabeled data based on it. Moreover, a modified methodology for the construction of the classification function, as outlined in [11], is presented.

2.1 Problem Definition

The process of label spreading can be described as follows. Given a dataset \mathcal{D} consisting of $n \in \mathbb{N}$ data points $x_1, \dots, x_l, x_{l+1}, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^m$, where the first $l < n$ data points are labeled and the remaining ones are unlabeled and a label set $L = \{1, \dots, c\}$, learn a classification function that is able to predict the labels of the unlabeled points [33]. Given that the classification function is learned from both labeled and unlabeled data, it constitutes a semi-supervised learning problem, which will now be further described.

2.2 Semi-Supervised Learning

Semi-supervised learning lies between supervised and unsupervised learning. In supervised learning, for every data point in the feature space, there exists a corresponding label. Therefore the dataset consists of tuples of observed data points and their corresponding label $(x_1, l_1), \dots, (x_n, l_n)$. The objective is to train a model f , that can accurately predict these labels for future observations, such that $f(x_i) = l_i$ is satisfied [12]. In contrast, in unsupervised learning, where solely observed data points x_1, \dots, x_n are provided, the objective is to discern relationships in these observations, enabling the partitioning of the observations into clusters and the identification of dependencies between them [4].

In semi-supervised learning, the data consists of both labeled observations and unlabeled observations $(x_1, l_1), \dots, (x_j, l_j), x_{j+1}, \dots, x_n$. In the subcategory of semi-supervised learning known as transductive learning, the goal is to apply the trained classifier to the unlabeled observations seen during the training phase [18]. This can be achieved

if certain assumptions regarding the data structure hold. Moreover techniques of both, supervised and unsupervised learning, need to be combined.

2.2.1 Assumptions

Semi-supervised learning methods should satisfy at least one of the following assumptions [18].

Smoothness Assumption: "If two points are close, then so should be their corresponding labels". This assumption corresponds to the fact that if the feature vectors of two data point are similar, then their corresponding label should not vary too much.

Cluster Assumption: "If points are in the same cluster, they are likely to be of the same label". This means each cluster should correspond to one of the labels, such that data points on the same cluster share the same label.

Manifold Assumption: "The high dimensional data lie on a lower dimensional manifold". This assumption enables the identification of a reduced-dimensional representation of the feature space X upon which the labeling is dependent.

Consider the *Two Moons* dataset, a toy dataset, illustrated in 2.2.1. For every point $(x_1, x_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2$, it should share the same label $l \in L = \{0, 1\}$ as the nearby points, which matches with the assumption of consistency. Additionally all points on the same moon should have the same label, referring to the cluster assumption.

Figure 2.2.1: *Two Moons* dataset with noise = 0.1.

In summary these assumptions ensure the feasibility of extracting information about the data from both the labeled data and the underlying data structure. This enables the provision of labels for the unlabeled data. This leads back to the problem of label spreading, where the aim is to propagate the labels of labeled data points to unlabeled data points. When considering the label spreading task, it is assumed that all three assumptions hold.

2.3 Graph Laplacian

These following explanations and definitions will be essential in the upcoming chapters to provide a more detailed explanation of the label spreading method.

For the following definitions let $G = (V, E, W)$ be a graph with n vertices and a symmetric weight matrix W with $W_{u,v} \geq 0$ and $W_{u,u} = 0 \forall u, v \in V$.

Degree of G. The degree of a vertex v is defined as $d_v = \sum_u W_{v,u}$.

Adjacency matrix of G. The adjacency matrix of a graph G is a matrix A with:

$$A_{i,j} = \begin{cases} W_{i,j}, & \text{if } (i, j) \in E, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The Laplacian of a graph and the normalized Laplacian can now be defined.

(Normalized) Laplacian matrix of G. The Laplacian matrix of a graph is defined as

$$L = D - A,$$

where D is a diagonal matrix where the (i, i) -element is equal to the degree of vertex i .

The normalized Laplacian matrix of a graph is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &= D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot L \cdot D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= I - D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot A \cdot D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

The Laplace matrix of a graph receives its name due to its relationship with the Laplace operator $\Delta = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\delta^2}{\delta^2 x_i}$ in continuous space [25]. It holds that the normalized Laplacian is a symmetric positive semi-definite matrix and its eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_n$ satisfy $0 \leq \lambda_i \leq 2$ [25]. Another method of expressing the normalized Laplacian matrix is by its spectral decomposition

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^n \phi_i \cdot \lambda_i \cdot \phi_i^\top$$

where ϕ_i denotes the i -th eigenvector. From this expression, it is possible to derive the relation to the following heat equation:

$$\frac{\delta h_\alpha}{\delta \alpha} = -\mathcal{L} \cdot h_\alpha$$

where the solution h_α denotes the heat kernel at time α . It holds that the solution is given by exponentiating the Laplacian eigenspectrum [1]. It follows:

$$h_\alpha = \sum_{i=1}^{|V|} e^{-\lambda_i \cdot \alpha} \cdot \phi_i \cdot \phi_i^T = e^{-\alpha \cdot \mathcal{L}} = I - \alpha \cdot \mathcal{L} + \frac{(-\alpha)^2}{2!} \cdot \mathcal{L}^2 + \dots,$$

with $h_0 = I$. If α tends to zero then

$$h_\alpha \approx I - \alpha \cdot \mathcal{L},$$

therefore the heat kernel only depends on the local connectivity of the graph. If α tends to infinity

$$h_\alpha \approx e^{-\lambda_m \cdot \alpha} \cdot \phi_m \cdot \phi_m^T,$$

where λ_m is the smallest non zero eigenvalue and ϕ_m the corresponding eigenvector. Note that ϕ_m is the Fiedler vector which can be used to divide a graph into clusters. This means that the heat kernel depends on the global structure of the graph [1].

Following from this, we can observe that the Laplacian is associated with the rate of dissipation of heat [5].

2.4 Classification Function

A dataset \mathcal{D} consisting of $n \in \mathbb{N}$ data points $x_1, \dots, x_l, x_{l+1}, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^m$, where the first $l < n$ data points are labeled and the remaining ones are unlabeled and a label set $L = \{1, \dots, c\}$ is provided. A classification function can then be notated as a non-negative $(n \times c)$ matrix F . Let \mathcal{F} define the set of classification functions, a special case of a classification function is a matrix $Y \in \mathcal{F}$ where $Y_{i,j} = 1$ if x_i is labeled as $y_i = j$ and $Y_{i,j} = 0$ otherwise. The label of a data point x_i is then predicted as follows

$$y_i = \arg \max_{j=1, \dots, c} F_{i,j}.$$

The classification function F is constructed graph-based. Each data point x_i is conceptualized as a node in a graph (X, E, W) , with edges representing connections between them. The weight of these edges signifies the strength of the connection. Here, the strength of the connection between two data points is defined by the euclidean distance separating them, corresponding to their similarity. The degree of similarity between two data points is reflected in the distance between them, with greater similarities

leading to shorter distances and a correspondingly stronger connection. Therefore the weights of the edges are defined by the following affinity matrix W of the graph (X, E, W) .

$$W_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma^2), & i \neq j, \\ 0, & i = j, \end{cases}$$

where σ depends on the underlying structure of the graph. Its symmetrical normalization is

$$S = D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot W \cdot D^{-\frac{1}{2}},$$

where D is a diagonal matrix with the (i, i) -element being equal to the sum of the i -th row of W . It is worth noting that S is equal to the normalized Laplacian matrix of the graph (X, E, W) .

A classification function can then be built utilizing the iterative method

$$F(t + 1) = \alpha \cdot S \cdot F(t) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot Y.$$

The first term refers to propagating the information of labeled data points to its neighbors which is done symmetrically by S , weighted by $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. The parameter α controls the intensity of the spreading, as α approaches one, more information gets disseminated. A data point thus propagates its information more strongly to similar data points than to data points that are very dissimilar, which aligns with the construction of the affinity matrix. The second term saves the initial information about the labels. As a starting value, $F(0) = Y$ is a suitable choice. It should also be noted that this iterative method can be interpreted as a random walk over the graph [33].

Algorithm 2.4.1 Label Spreading

Require: X, L, Y, α

- 1: $W_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma^2), & i \neq j \\ 0, & i = j \end{cases}$
 - 2: $D \leftarrow \text{diag}(W\mathbf{1}_n)$
 - 3: $S \leftarrow D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot W \cdot D^{-\frac{1}{2}}$
 - 4: $F(0) = Y$
 - 5: $t = 0$
 - 6: **while** F did not converge **do**
 - 7: $F(t + 1) \leftarrow \alpha \cdot S \cdot F(t) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot Y$
 - 8: $t \leftarrow t + 1$
 - 9: **end while**
 - 10: **return** F
-

The limit of the iterative method is given by

$$(2.4.1) \quad F^* = (I - \alpha S)^{-1} \cdot Y.$$

The proof is provided in [33]. The classification function can now be calculated by matrix inversion, which has a calculation effort of $\mathcal{O}(n^3)$. Furthermore it can be seen that the information of the data is disseminated throughout the graph via the heat kernel $(I - \alpha S)^{-1}$. Therefore, label spreading is related to the dissipation of heat. F^* is the desired classification function and the label of a data point x_i can be predicted by $y_i = \arg \max_{j=1, \dots, c} F_{i,j}^*$. This implies that the label of an unlabeled data point x_i is predicted based on the class from which it received the most information.

2.4.1 Regularization Framework

As previously described in Section 2.2.1, it is desirable that a classification function is sufficiently smooth. To validate this, we can construct a cost function to assess both the smoothness assumption and the stability of the classification function with respect to the initial labels. This stability is crucial for effectively leveraging the information already provided.

Definition 2.1. *The cost function of a classification function F is given by*

$$\mathcal{Q}(F) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^n W_{i,j} \cdot \left\| \frac{1}{\sqrt{D_{i,i}}} F_i - \frac{1}{\sqrt{D_{j,j}}} F_j \right\|^2 + \mu \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \|F_i - Y_i\|^2 \right),$$

with $\mu > 0$ the regularization parameter.

The first term of the cost function refers to the smoothness assumption. It is given by the sum of local changes between nearby points. The second term of the function checks the deviation from the initial label. It follows that a suitable classification function should minimize the cost function. It can be proven [33] that

$$F^* = \arg \min_{F \in \mathcal{F}} \mathcal{Q}(F).$$

From this it follows that the constructed classification function is indeed the best possible in terms of the cost function.

2.4.2 Extension

In the subsequent subsection, an alteration to the iterative method to build the classification function will be examined, aimed at enhancing the computational efficiency of label spreading, introduced in [11].

Instead of constructing a full symmetric affinity matrix W , a sparse affinity matrix A can be constructed based on the k -nearest neighbors $\mathbf{NN}_k(x_i)$ of each node x_i with

$$a_{ij} = \begin{cases} s(x_i, x_j), & i \neq j \text{ and } x_j \in \mathbf{NN}_k(x_i), \\ 0, & \text{else,} \end{cases}$$

where $s : \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a symmetric, positive similarity measure. It is argued in [11] that setting up a dense affinity matrix is not a feasible approach, whereas setting up the affinity matrix with the k -nearest neighbors approach is an efficient method. The symmetric form of the affinity matrix A is then obtained via

$$W = A + A^\top.$$

It follows that W is a symmetric non-negative adjacency matrix, which is now sparse. It remains to solve again the linear system of equations

$$(I - \alpha S) \cdot F^* = Y$$

to obtain the classification function. In [11], it is recommended to employ the conjugate gradient method to solve the system, which is known to be faster than utilizing the iterative method. Therefore the label spreading algorithm, Algorithm 2.4.1, could be further extended as follows.

Algorithm 2.4.2 Label Spreading Extension

Require: $X, L, Y, \alpha, k, n_{classes}$

- 1: $a_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma^2), & i \neq j \text{ and } x_j \in \mathbf{NN}_k(x_i) \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}$
 - 2: $W \leftarrow A + A^\top$
 - 3: $D \leftarrow \text{diag}(W\mathbf{1}_n)$
 - 4: $S \leftarrow D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot W \cdot D^{-\frac{1}{2}}$
 - 5: **for** c in $n_{classes}$ **do**
 - 6: **Solve** $(I - \alpha S) \cdot F_c^* = Y_c$ with conjugate gradient method($(I - \alpha S), Y_c$)
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **return** F^*
-

2.4.3 Analysis of the System Matrix

The linear system of equations represented by equation (2.4.1) constitutes the primary component of the label spreading algorithm. Consequently, it is of interest to analyse the properties of the system matrix $(I - \alpha S)$. The properties of the matrix indicate which methods are suitable for solving the linear system of equations. These methods will be explained in more detail later on. The following provides a list of the parameters of the label spreading algorithm on which the matrix depends, along with an explanation of their influence on the matrix.

1. The number of data points n_{data} in the dataset determines the size of the matrix.
2. The number of nearest neighbors, k , exerts a significant influence on the sparsity of the matrix. A small number of nearest neighbors relative to the size of the matrix results in a sparse matrix. Conversely, as the number of nearest neighbors increases, the matrix contains an increasing number of non-zero entries. In the

most extreme case, where the number of neighbors is equal to the number of data points, the result is a dense matrix. Another consequence of the number of nearest neighbors is that they influence the distribution of the eigenvalues. As illustrated in Figure 2.4.2, for a small number of nearest neighbors, the distribution of the eigenvalues is more dispersed. In contrast, for an increasing number of nearest neighbors, the distribution is more centered around one, with fewer eigenvalues found at the margins of the distribution.

3. The value of the spreading parameter $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ has a significant impact on the condition number of the matrix, as illustrated in the Figure 2.4.1. As α approaches 1, the condition number of the matrix increases exponentially. This can lead to numerical difficulties when attempting to solve the linear system of equations.

Another important aspect to consider is that the matrix $(I - \alpha S)$ is positive definite. This assertion is valid because S is similar to a stochastic matrix [33]. In this context, the eigenvalues are always less than or equal to 1. Consequently, the eigenvalues of S are likewise always less than or equal to 1 due to this similarity. This implies that the eigenvalues of αS lie within the interval $[-\alpha, \alpha]$, and consequently, the eigenvalues of $(I - \alpha S)$ reside in the interval $[1 - \alpha, 1 + \alpha]$. Given that $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, it follows that the matrix possesses only positive eigenvalues, rendering it positive definite.

Figure 2.4.1: Impact of the parameter α on the condition number of the system matrix. The condition number is computed as the ratio of the absolute value of the largest eigenvalue to the absolute value of the smallest eigenvalue.

(a) Occurrence of eigenvalues for 8 nearest neighbors.

(b) Occurrence of eigenvalues for 500 nearest neighbors.

Figure 2.4.2: A comparison of the occurrence of various eigenvalues. The matrix was generated on the *Two Moons* dataset, incorporating the noise parameter of 0.1 and 8000 data points. The parameter α was set to 0.99.

3 Probabilistic Label Spreading

This section will elucidate the extension of label spreading for the application of so-called probabilistic labels, based on [3]. Initially, the components of a probabilistic dataset will be precisely explained. Subsequently, the origin of these labels will be clarified. Expanding on this, further insight will be provided regarding the modification of the label spreading method, which is outlined in Section 2, in order to utilise it for probabilistic labels.

3.1 Probabilistic Labels

Probabilistic labels vary from the labels examined previously in that each data point does not have a precise label assignment but rather receives a probability distribution across all potential classes. This results in the following setting.

A probabilistic dataset \mathcal{D} consists of data points $x_1, \dots, x_l, x_{l+1}, \dots, x_n \in \mathbb{R}^m$, where each data point x_i has a label $p_i^* = (p_{i,1}^*, \dots, p_{i,c}^*) \in [0, 1]^c$ with $\sum_{j=1}^c p_{i,j}^* = 1, \forall i = 1, \dots, l$. $p_{i,j}^*$ denotes the probability that x_i belongs to class j . This implies that a label p_i^* represents a probability distribution for x_i across the possible classes $L = \{1, \dots, c\}$.

Figure 3.1.1: Probabilistic labels for the *Two Moons* dataset.

In Figure 3.1.1, probabilistic labels for the *Two Moons* dataset with noise of 0.1 are illustrated. A probability nearing 1 signifies that the label pertains to class one, whereas a probability approaching zero indicates affiliation with class zero. Probabilistic labels can arise in various ways. This work focuses on image classification, particularly on the use case when images are captured in poor quality and the assignment to a class is not clear-cut. Here, it is helpful to not simply assign one class, but to provide information on the probability with which the image can be assigned to each class. As a result, the assignment of the label to each data point is accompanied by a measure of confidence, which is determined by its density.

Note that the true probability distribution p_i^* for each x_i cannot be known in practice, hence it must be estimated by a distribution \hat{p}_i . One approach to estimate the true probability distribution of a data point is the crowdsourcing approach. In this approach, different individuals label the same data point x_i , and the resulting probability distribution arises from the relative frequencies with which it is assigned to each class. This method can be described as independently and identically distributed multinomial sampling according to p_i^* . It should hold that

$$\hat{p}_i \rightarrow p_i^*$$

if x_i is labeled infinitely often. This indicates the goal of conducting as many crowdsourcing experiments as possible on each data point to reduce epistemic uncertainty, that arises from the insufficient multiplicity of the label assignment.

3.2 Probabilistic Label Spreading Algorithm

As previously explained, the goal is to estimate the true distribution of each data point as accurately as possible by conducting as many crowdsourcing experiments as feasible. However, this approach is highly costly and impractical in real-world scenarios. Nonetheless, the label spreading method can be extended for probabilistic labels. In this context, an edge in the graph now represents a weighted crowdsourcing experiment, facilitating the convergence of distributions as the number of conducted experiments increases. This is achieved by disseminating information throughout the graph. Therefore Algorithm 3.2.1 presents the label spreading method extended for probabilistic labels.

Algorithm 3.2.1 Probabilistic Label Spreading

```

1: Data:  $\mathcal{D}, \alpha \in (0, 1), k, n_{samples}, n_{data}$ 
2: Result:  $\hat{p}_i = (p_{i,1}, \dots, p_{i,c}) \forall i = 1, \dots, n_{data}$ 
3:  $a_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma^2), & i \neq j \text{ and } x_j \in \mathbf{NN}_k(x_i) \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}$ 
4:  $W \leftarrow (A + A^\top)/2$ 
5:  $D \leftarrow \text{diag}(W\mathbf{1}_n)$ 
6:  $S \leftarrow D^{-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot W \cdot D^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ 
7: Initialize  $N, Y^1, \dots, Y^c = (0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{data}}$ 
8: for  $s = 1, \dots, n_{samples}$  do
9:    $z \sim U(\{1, \dots, n_{data}\})$ 
10:  Draw  $l = c$  with  $c \sim p_z^*$ 
11:   $\phi \leftarrow (I - \alpha S)^{-1} \cdot e_z$  with  $e_z \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{data}}$ 
12:   $\phi \leftarrow \phi / \|\phi\|_\infty$ 
13:   $Y^l \leftarrow Y^l + \phi$ 
14:   $N \leftarrow N + \phi$ 
15: end for
16: for  $i = 1, \dots, n_{data}$  do
17:  If  $N_i \neq 0$  then
18:    for  $l = 1, \dots, c$  do
19:       $\hat{p}_{i,l} \leftarrow Y_i^l / N_i$ 
20:    end for
21:  else
22:    for  $l = 1, \dots, c$  do
23:       $\hat{p}_{i,l} \leftarrow 1/c$ 
24:    end for
25: end for

```

The initial modification to the label spreading algorithm involves selecting the affinity matrix W , which now follows the approach outlined in [24]. This adjustment aims to ensure a symmetric weight matrix and bidirectional edges. Additionally, as previously noted in [11], an edge between vertices i and j only exists if j is a k -nearest neighbor of i or if i is a k -nearest neighbor of j . Note that, as a result of these modifications, it is possible for a node in the graph to have more than k -nearest neighbor edges. The entries of the affinity matrix are now

$$(3.2.1) \quad W_{i,j} = \begin{cases} \exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma^2), & i \neq j, x_j \in \mathbf{NN}_k(x_i), x_i \in \mathbf{NN}_k(x_j), \\ (\exp(-\|x_i - x_j\|^2/2\sigma^2)/2), & i \neq j, x_j \in \mathbf{NN}_k(x_i), x_i \notin \mathbf{NN}_k(x_j), \\ 0, & i = j. \end{cases}$$

Figure 3.2.1 displays the underlying graph structure alongside the probabilistic labels for the *Two Moons* dataset.

Figure 3.2.1: Graph structure of the probabilistic label spreading method for the *Two Moons* dataset.

The algorithm performs $n_{samples}$ crowdsourcing experiments by randomly selecting samples from the dataset with a uniform distribution. If no crowdsourcing experiment has yet been performed on a data point, the uniform distribution applies. A single crowdsourcing experiment on x_z is then conducted by $l = c$ with $c \sim p_z^*$, where a class l is drawn with the probability of the true distribution. As the true probabilistic labels are unknown, they are generated in advance by a neural network. Afterwards, the information of this experiment is spread through the graph by solving the equation: $\phi = (I - \alpha S)^{-1} \cdot e_z$. This system of equations must be solved separately for each conducted crowdsourcing experiment, resulting in $n_{samples}$ times. The amount of information propagated to all other data points is then saved in ϕ and afterwards is normalized by $\phi \leftarrow \phi / \|\phi\|_\infty$, such that ϕ_i denotes the fraction of information the experiment spread to all other data points. The total fraction of information a data point x_i received from all other samples is saved in N_i and the fraction of information of belonging to a class l is given by Y_i^l . After conducting all $n_{samples}$ crowdsourcing experiments, the estimated probability distributions of all n_{data} data points in the dataset are calculated by the relative frequencies $\hat{p}_{i,l} = Y_i^l / N_i \forall i = 1, \dots, n_{data}$.

To summarize the method, in probabilistic label spreading, the spreading between two data points can be viewed as a crowdsourcing experiment, which is weighted by the similarity of the data points. Therefore, conducting an experiment on a data point leads to conducting a weighted crowdsourcing experiment on similar data points.

In Figure 3.2.2, the graph structure for the *Two Moons* dataset is illustrated, demonstrating how a single data point propagates its information throughout the graph

with $\alpha = 0.999$. The feedback indicates how much information a data point receives from this particular data point.

Figure 3.2.2: Spreading the information of a data point through the graph of the probabilistic label spreading method for the *Two moons* dataset.

In conclusion, probabilistic label spreading is an efficacious methodology for the generation and improvement of probabilistic labels. By efficaciously exchanging information among the data, the necessity for human-conducted crowdsourcing experiments can be reduced, resulting in considerable cost savings while reducing the epistemic uncertainty stemming from incomplete information. This makes the utilization of probabilistic labels feasible, offering substantial benefits by enhancing the interpretability of labels assigned to data points and ensuring reliability.

Remark 3.1 (Placement within the Framework of Machine Learning). *Probabilistic label spreading can be placed within the framework of machine learning as follows. Since its goal is to improve or create labels for data, it naturally fits into the domain of classification problems. Since it involves transferring information from one data point to another during training, it operates as a form of transductive learning. In addition, because it can use both labeled and unlabeled data, including weakly labeled data, it also has ties to semi-supervised learning.*

4 Dimensionality Reduction Methods

This chapter presents a selection of methods for reducing the dimensionality of high-dimensional input data in machine learning. In numerous applications the input space X comprises a large number of features, resulting in high-dimensional input vectors. For instance, in the field of image classification, the features consist of the pixel values of the image, which nowadays amount to millions of values for regular cameras [13]. The curse of dimensionality is a problem that arises due to the exponential growth of the input space with the dimension. As a result, a large amount of data is required to cover the input space adequately. This leads to the issue that if there is only a limited amount of data, they will be far apart in space, violating the assumption of local consistency in label spreading [16]. Therefore, it is necessary to use dimensionality reduction methods that can map high-dimensional data to a lower-dimensional representation. Therefore, a mapping function $f : X \rightarrow Z$ is learned, that transforms a high dimensional vector $x \in X$ of dimension m into a low dimensional representation $z \in Z$ of dimension $d \ll m$.

4.1 Principle Component Analysis

The following explanation of principal component analysis (PCA) is based on [16]. Given a dataset \mathcal{D} consisting of n observations $(x_1, \dots, x_n) = X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, PCA aims to find a set of linearly uncorrelated variables, called principal components, that capture the maximum variance in the data.

PCA achieves this by performing an eigenvalue decomposition of the covariance matrix of the feature space X . The principal components are the eigenvectors of this covariance matrix, ordered by the magnitude of their corresponding eigenvalues. Each principal component represents a direction in the original feature space, and the variance of the data along that direction. By retaining only the top d principal components PCA allows for dimensionality reduction while preserving as much variance as possible in the data. This can be expressed mathematically as follows.

Let $W \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$ be the matrix whose columns are the top d eigenvectors of the covariance matrix of X . Then, the feature space $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d}$ with reduced dimension is obtained by a linear projection from X onto the subspace spanned by these eigenvectors

$$Z = XW.$$

4.2 Isometric Feature Mapping

Isometric feature mapping (ISOMAP) is an approach used to address dimensionality reduction problems by learning the underlying global geometry of the dataset. Additional

information about ISOMAP can be found in [28]. Unlike principal component analysis, ISOMAP can uncover nonlinear degrees of freedom, allowing it to learn a wide range of nonlinear manifolds. This is achieved by preserving the intrinsic geometry of the data, captured in the geodesic manifold distances between all pairs of data points. ISOMAP comprises three steps to obtain the lower-dimensional representation of the input feature space X . In the first step, ISOMAP identifies which points are neighbors on the manifold based on the distances between points in X . This can be achieved by connecting each data point to its k -nearest neighbors or to all data points within a radius ϵ . These neighborhood relations are represented as a weighted graph over all data points, with edges assigned weights equal to the euclidean distances $d_X(x_i, x_j)$. In the second step, ISOMAP estimates the geodesic distances between all data points on the manifold by computing the shortest path distances on the graph $d_G(x_i, x_j)$. Finally, in the third step, the classical dimensionality reduction method *multidimensional scaling* is applied to the matrix of graph distances $W = \{d_G(x_i, x_j)\}$. This process results in an embedding in a d -dimensional Euclidean space that best preserves the estimated intrinsic geometry of the manifolds.

Figure 4.2.1: An example of the *Swiss roll* from [28]. Figure A demonstrates that the Euclidean distance (indicated by the blue dashed line) between two points in high-dimensional space can appear small, whereas the distance on the non-linear manifold (represented by the blue solid curve) is large. Figure B shows the neighborhood graph G and the shortest path between the two point is represented by the red line. The two-dimensional embedding is displayed in Figure C. The red line represents the shortest distance between the points in the embedding space, while the blue line is an approximation of the true geodesic distance.

4.3 Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection

Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) [15] is a graph-based algorithm for dimension reduction that draws upon manifold learning principles and ideas from topological analysis. In order to reduce the dimensionality of the data $X = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$, UMAP begins by constructing a high-dimensional graph representation of the data and then optimizes a low-dimensional graph to closely mirror its structure. In the high-dimensional graph G , the weights indicate the likelihood of two data points being

connected. To determine these connections, UMAP extends a radius outward from each point, connecting points only if their radii overlap. The radius is chosen locally for each point x_i based on the distance to its k -nearest neighbors $\{x_{i,1}, \dots, x_{i,k}\}$, with an increasing radius indicating a decreasing likelihood of a connection. The radius for a data point x_i is defined as

$$p_i = \min\{d(x_i, x_{i,j}) | 1 \leq j \leq k, d(x_i, x_{i,j}) > 0\},$$

with a dissimilarity measure $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$. The radii of all data points can now be used to construct a directed graph $\vec{G} = (V, E, W)$, where the nodes are given by $V := X$ and the edges by $E := \{(x_i, x_{i,j}) | 1 \leq j \leq k, 1 \leq i \leq n\}$. The weights are defined as

$$W((x_i, x_{i,j})) = \exp\left(\frac{-\max(0, d(x_i, x_{i,j}) - p_i)}{\sigma_i}\right).$$

Here, σ_i denotes a normalization factor for the corresponding data point. The UMAP graph G is then an undirected graph whose adjacency matrix is given by $B := A + A^T - A \circ A^T$, with A being the adjacency matrix of \vec{G} . Subsequently, UMAP projects the graph into a lower-dimensional space so that the layout of the low-dimensional graph closely resembles that of the high-dimensional one. It is worth noting that UMAP highly depends on its hyperparameters, including the number of k -nearest neighbors and the minimal distance in the low-dimensional space, which controls how closely points are clustered together. A more detailed explanation of UMAP can be found in [15].

4.4 Neural Network CLIP

CLIP stands for Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training. A detailed description of CLIP is provided in [22]. Unlike other methods that focus solely on understanding image features and predicting predefined classes, CLIP takes a different approach. It learns from both the pictures and the text associated with them which is a so called contrastive learning method. This enables it to determine the appropriate caption for each image. The model is trained on a dataset of n equals 400 million pairs of images and text $\{(x_i, t_i) \in X \times T | i = 1, \dots, n\}$ collected from the internet and works as follows. CLIP trains an image encoder and a text encoder in parallel. The image encoder $f : X \rightarrow Z$ reduces the image into the lower-dimensional feature space, while the text encoder $g : T \rightarrow Z$ processes the caption associated with the image. These two encoders work together to embed both the image and its corresponding caption into a unified embedding space Z . Given a batch of N image-text pairs, the two embedders are then trained to maximize the cosine similarity $\delta : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, 1]$, a measure of similarity, between correct pairs of image and text, which are N^2 pairs, while minimizing the cosine similarity between the $N^2 - N$ incorrect pairs. The objective is to attain

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(f(x_i), g(t_j)) &\rightarrow 1 \quad \forall i = j, \\ \delta(f(x_i), g(t_j)) &\rightarrow 0 \quad \forall i \neq j. \end{aligned}$$

A symmetric cross-entropy loss is then optimized over these similarity scores. After training, CLIP is capable of determining the most suitable caption from a predefined set of classes for a given image. This approach is also applicable to previously unseen predefined classes, which is referred to as a zero-shot prediction. In this work, the image encoder of CLIP is used as a dimensionality reduction method.

Figure 4.4.1: Summary of CLIP taken from [22]. The left-hand image illustrates the training phase where the blue boxes represent the image text pairs to be maximized. The right-hand image shows the prediction process for an image and predefined classes. The blue box represents the class that best fits the given image.

5 Iterative Linear Solvers

This chapter presents several iterative methods for solving linear systems of equations and their properties. These methods are employed when direct solvers are infeasible due to their time consumption, which can occur in the context of large linear systems of equations. Furthermore, for sparse linear systems of equations, direct solvers do not leverage the special structure of the matrix to reduce computation time. First, basic iterative solvers such as the Jacobi and the Gauß-Seidel method are discussed with the help of [32]. Then, Krylov subspace methods are introduced, derived from [29, 2, 23], which are known to be faster than the basic iterative solvers. Afterwards, algebraic multigrid methods are studied, with the help of [30]. These methods are particularly effective for solving large, sparse systems of equations, offering a convergence rate that is independent of the size of the system. Furthermore, they preserve more information about the problem than Krylov subspace methods. Finally, to further increase the robustness and efficiency of iterative methods, preconditioning is discussed, based on [23, 2].

Given a regular matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and a right-hand side $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the objective is to find an accurate approximation to the solution $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ of the equation

$$Ax = b.$$

The approximate solution found is noted as \hat{x} . The error vector is then given by $e := x - \hat{x}$ and the residual vector by $r := b - A\hat{x}$.

5.1 Basic Iterative Methods

Iterative methods compute an approximation of a linear systems solution by starting with an initial vector $x^{(0)}$ and building approximations $x^{(k)}$ iteratively, which are approximations to the exact solution. They do this by successively computing the residual vector of the last approximate solution and using it to update it

$$(5.1.1) \quad \begin{aligned} x^{(k)} &= x^{(k-1)} + C(b - Ax^{(k-1)}) \\ &= Bx^{(k-1)} + c \end{aligned}$$

with $C \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B = I - CA$ and $c = Cb$.

The matrix C can be chosen differently and leads to different iterative methods. Consider the decomposition of the matrix $A = L + D + R$ into the lower triangular part L , the diagonal part D and the upper triangular part R .

Definition 5.1 (Jacobi method). *The Jacobi method solves the linear system of equations $Ax = b$ by iteratively computing*

$$x^{(k)} = x^{(k-1)} + D^{-1}(b - Ax^{(k-1)}).$$

By introducing a damping parameter $\omega \in (0, 1]$, the damped Jacobi method is given by

$$x^{(k)} = x^{(k-1)} + \omega D^{-1}(b - Ax^{(k-1)}).$$

Definition 5.2 (Gauß-Seidel method). *The Gauß-Seidel method solves the linear system of equations $Ax = b$ by iteratively computing*

$$x^{(k)} = x^{(k-1)} + (D + L)^{-1}(b - Ax^{(k-1)}).$$

Iterative methods of the form (5.1.1) converge to the exact solution for arbitrary start vectors if and only if the spectral radius of B is smaller than one. This condition holds for both the Jacobi and the Gauß-Seidel method.

The Gauß-Seidel method is known to converge faster than the Jacobi method [23]. Conversely, the Jacobi method can be parallelized in a natural way, which is not the case with the Gauß-Seidel method. In order to make the Gauß-Seidel method parallelizable, a *multicolor* approach can be employed. The multicolor Gauß-Seidel parallelises the Gauß-Seidel procedure by grouping variables into distinct subsets, or *colors*, and updating each subset independently in parallel. This parallel updating of different subsets can reduce the number of iterations required for convergence compared to the sequential updating of Gauß-Seidel. The term *multicolor* refers to the coloring scheme used to partition variables into subsets. Different coloring schemes can be employed based on the problem's structure and the underlying matrix. Additional information about the multicolor ansatz can be found in [23].

Sometimes, it may not be necessary to calculate the exact solution, which can be time-consuming. Instead, it may suffice to know the solution to a desired level of accuracy. Therefore, a termination criterion is needed. One potential approach is to ascertain whether the relative residual norm is below a specified threshold

$$\frac{\|r^{(k)}\|}{\|b\|} < \tau.$$

An additional option is to limit the maximum number of iterations. This way, an iterative method will stop once it reaches this specific iteration count.

5.1.1 Block Relaxation Schemes

The Jacobi and Gauß-Seidel methods can both be generalized to block relaxation schemes [23]. The matrix A , the right-hand side b , and the solution vector x are partitioned into

p components

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} A_{1,1} & A_{1,2} & \dots & A_{1,p} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{p,1} & A_{p,2} & \dots & A_{p,p} \end{pmatrix}, x = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_p \end{pmatrix}, b = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_p \end{pmatrix},$$

such that

$$(Ax)_i = \sum_{j=1}^p A_{i,j}x_j.$$

The components are then updated simultaneously, here for example with the block Jacobi method

$$x_i^{(k)} = x_i^{(k-1)} + D_i^{-1}(\beta_i - \sum_{j=1}^p A_{i,j}x_j^{(k-1)}),$$

$i = 1, \dots, p$. The Gauß-Seidel method operates analogously.

5.2 Krylov Subspace Methods

Another class of iterative methods that are faster than those discussed so far are Krylov subspace methods. A Krylov subspace is defined as follows.

Definition 5.3 (Krylov subspace). *The k -th Krylov subspace $K^{(k)}(A, v) \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, generated by $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $v \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is given by*

$$K^{(k)}(A, v) := \text{span}(v, Av, A^2v, \dots, A^{k-1}v).$$

A Krylov subspace method is defined as an iterative process of computing approximations of the solution from a starting vector such that

$$x^{(k)} = x^{(0)} + t^{(k)}, \quad t^{(k)} \in K^{(k)}(A, r),$$

with $r := b - Ax^{(0)}$. Therefore the method seeks an approximate solution $x^{(k)}$ from the affine subspace $x^{(0)} + K^{(k)}(A, r)$ of the dimension n by imposing the Petrov-Galerkin condition $b - Ax^{(k)} \perp L$ where L is another subspace of dimension n . This means that the residual vector must be orthogonal to all vectors of this subspace. Different versions of Krylov subspace methods arise from different choices of the subspace L .

5.2.1 Generalized Minimal Residual

In the Generalized Minimal Residual Method (GMRES), the subspace L is defined as $L = AK^{(k)}(A, v_1)$, with $v_1 = r^{(0)} / \|r^{(0)}\|_2$. In each iteration k of the GMRES algorithm, $x^{(k)}$ is computed to minimize the Euclidean norm of the residual vector $\|r^{(k)}\|_2 = \|b - Ax^{(k)}\|_2$.

This minimization is usually accomplished by utilizing the Arnoldi iteration [23] to create an orthonormal basis $V^{(k)} = \{v_1, \dots, v_k\}$ for $K^{(k)}(A, v_1)$ and then solving a small least squares problem that involves the Hessenberg matrix $H^{(k)}$ generated by the Arnoldi iteration. Therefore, in each iteration the equivalent problem

$$J(y) = \|b - Ax\|_2 = \|b - A(x^{(0)} + V^{(k)}y)\|_2 = \|\beta e_1 - \bar{H}^{(k)}y\|_2,$$

is minimized, with $e_1 = (1, 0, \dots, 0)$, $\beta = \|r^{(0)}\|_2$, $y \in \mathbb{R}^k$ and $\bar{H}^{(k)} = (h_{i,j})$ the $(k+1) \times k$ upper Hessenberg matrix whose entries are computed by the Arnoldi algorithm and $H^{(k)}$ the $k \times k$ submatrix extracted from $\bar{H}^{(k)}$ by deleting its last row. The definition of the upper Hessian matrix can be found in [23]. The GMRES approximation is the unique vector $x^{(0)} + K^{(k)}$ that minimizes $\|b - Ax^{(k)}\|_2$ by using $x^{(k)} = x^{(0)} + V^{(k)}y^{(k)}$, where $y^{(k)}$ minimizes $J(y) = \|\beta e_1 - \bar{H}^{(k)}y\|_2$.

The GMRES algorithm is used to solve large linear systems of equations. Additional details about the method can be found in [2, 23]. In Algorithm 5.2.1, the GMRES algorithm is presented.

Algorithm 5.2.1 GMRES

Require: Matrix A , right-hand side vector b , initial guess $x^{(0)}$, maximum iteration count m

- 1: Compute $r^{(0)} = b - Ax^{(0)}$, $\beta = \|r^{(0)}\|_2$, and $v_1 = r^{(0)}/\beta$
 - 2: **for** $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$ **do**
 - 3: Compute $w^{(k)} := Av_1$
 - 4: **for** $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$ **do**
 - 5: $h_{i,k} := (w^{(k)}, v_i)$
 - 6: $w^{(k)} := w^{(k)} - h_{i,k}v_i$
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: $h_{k+1,k} = \|w^{(k)}\|_2$. If $h_{k+1,k} = 0$, set $m := k$ and go to line 11.
 - 9: $v_{k+1} = w^{(k)}/h_{k+1,k}$
 - 10: **end for**
 - 11: Define the $(m+1) \times m$ Hessenberg matrix $\bar{H}^{(m)} = \{h_{i,k}\}_{1 \leq i \leq m+1, 1 \leq k \leq m}$.
 - 12: Compute $y^{(m)}$ the minimizer of $\|\beta e_1 - \bar{H}^{(m)}y\|_2$, and $x^{(0)} = x^{(0)} + V^{(m)}y^{(m)}$.
-

5.2.2 Conjugate Gradient Method

The conjugate gradient (CG) method is a Krylov subspace method used to solve linear systems with symmetric positive definite system matrices A . This means that $x^T Ax > 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^n \setminus \{0\}$ and $A^T = A$. Under the assumption of positive definiteness, the following norm is defined

$$\|x\|_A := \sqrt{x^T Ax}.$$

The conjugate gradient method can calculate the exact solution in n iterations if executed in exact arithmetic and is particularly effective for solving sparse linear systems of

equations. It holds that the conjugate gradient iteration generates a unique sequence of iterates $\{x^{(k)} \in K^{(k)}(A, r)\}$ such that at step k , the error $\|e^{(k)}\|_A = \|x - x^{(k)}\|_A$ is minimized. This is done by minimizing the equation

$$\phi(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^T Ax - x^T b.$$

It can be proven that $\|e^{(k)}\|_A^2 = 2\phi(x^{(k)}) + \text{const}$, so that minimizing $\phi(x^{(k)})$ leads to the minimization of $\|e^{(k)}\|_A$ [29].

Algorithm 5.2.2 CG

Require: Symmetric positive definite matrix A , right-hand side vector b , initial guess $x^{(0)}$, tolerance τ , maximum iteration count m

- 1: $r^{(0)} = b - Ax^{(0)}$
- 2: $d^{(0)} = r^{(0)}$
- 3: **for** $k = 0, 1, \dots, m$ **do**
- 4: $\alpha^{(k)} = \frac{(r^{(k)})^T r^{(k)}}{(d^{(k)})^T A d^{(k)}}$ ▷ step length
- 5: $x^{(k+1)} = x^{(k)} + \alpha^{(k)} d^{(k)}$ ▷ approximate solution
- 6: $r^{(k+1)} = r^{(k)} - \alpha^{(k)} A d^{(k)}$ ▷ residual
- 7: **if** $\|r^{(k+1)}\| / \|b\| < \tau$ **then**
- 8: **break**
- 9: **end if**
- 10: $\beta^{(k)} = \frac{(r^{(k+1)})^T r^{(k+1)}}{(r^{(k)})^T r^{(k)}}$ ▷ improvement of this step
- 11: $d^{(k+1)} = r^{(k+1)} + \beta^{(k)} d^{(k)}$ ▷ search direction
- 12: **end for**

In the following, results on the convergence rate of the CG method are presented.

Theorem 5.4. *If the CG iteration is applied to a linear system of equations $Ax = b$ with symmetric positive definite system matrix A , where A has 2-norm condition number κ . Then it holds*

$$\frac{\|e^{(k)}\|_A}{\|e^{(0)}\|_A} \leq 2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\kappa} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa} + 1} \right)^k.$$

Proof. [29] □

Theorem 5.4 implies that the convergence rate is dependent on the condition number of the matrix. It holds that

$$\frac{\sqrt{\kappa} - 1}{\sqrt{\kappa} + 1} \approx 1 - \frac{2}{\sqrt{\kappa}}$$

as $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore it implies that, if κ is large but not too large, convergence to a specific tolerance can be expected in $\mathcal{O}(\sqrt{\kappa})$ iterations. In [29] it is stated that the convergence rate also depends on the location of the spectrum of A . If the eigenvalues are grouped in small clusters or are well separated in the relative sense from the origin, the convergence is faster. The proof of this can be found in [29].

5.3 Algebraic Multigrid Methods

Since the 1990s, there has been a significant demand for efficient methods to solve large, sparse, and unstructured linear systems of equations. For such systems, which are of practical relevance, one-level methods have reached their limits. Therefore, hierarchical algorithms had to be developed to solve such systems of equations efficiently. Geometric multigrid methods [30] were developed to solve linear systems of equations that arise when solving partial differential equations by discretization approaches such as the finite difference method. The matrix of the system of equations contains the grid used to solve the differential equation, resulting in geometric properties that arise from its construction. Algebraic multigrid (AMG) methods [27], extend the classical idea of geometric multigrid to matrices without any geometrical background. AMG is a *plug-in* solver that can be applied directly to structured and unstructured matrices, making it practically relevant and providing robust solution methods.

The following section provides a detailed discussion of algebraic multigrid methods. It begins by explaining the concept of AMG and then delves into the components of the AMG algorithm. Afterwards, the entire AMG algorithm is presented.

5.3.1 Basic Idea of the Multigrid Approach

The multigrid approach is based on the following two principles.

Smoothing principle. Many classical iterative methods have a strong smoothing effect on the error of any approximation.

Coarse grid correction principle. A smooth error term is well approximated on a coarse grid and a coarse grid procedure is less expensive than a fine grid procedure.

In the context of AMG, a grid refers to a collection of variables or degrees of freedom of the system matrix A , with a coarse grid being a subset of these variables. From the principles above, it follows that if the error becomes smooth after a few iterations with an iterative method, it can be approximated on a coarse grid without losing information. Multigrid methods are efficient because of a specific procedure that follows the presented principles. By performing a Fourier expansion of an error, it is demonstrated that high-frequency error components rapidly decrease, while low-frequency error components remain relatively constant after a few steps of an iterative solver. Therefore, the convergence speed is dependent on the low-frequency error components. According to the theory, error components with high frequency are not representable on a coarser grid, while low-frequency components are representable but behave more like high-frequency components on the coarse grid. Therefore, they can be quickly smoothed on the coarser grid. Multigrid methods take advantage of these findings by smoothing the error on various coarse grids and covering all error components, resulting in rapid reduction of the total error. The smoothing procedure is depicted in Figure 5.3.1. Therefore, AMG

smooths errors on various coarser grid levels and computes the solution of the coarsest grid directly once a sufficiently coarse grid is reached. The solution is then interpolated through the grid levels and returned to the original grid to obtain the desired solution of the original system.

Figure 5.3.1: The figure illustrates the impact of a few iterations with the Gauß-Seidel method. The right image depicts the error of the initial guess, while the middle image shows the error after five iterations of the Gauß-Seidel method. The right image displays the error after ten iterations [30].

To solve a linear system of equations $Ax = b$, multigrid methods will use the residual equation $Ae = r$, which is equivalent to solving the original equation.

$$Ae = r \Leftrightarrow A(x - \hat{x}) = b - A\hat{x} \Leftrightarrow Ax = b$$

5.3.2 Algebraic Smoothness

In accordance with the smoothing principle, it is necessary to define the concept of smoothness. In the algebraic multigrid setting, an error is considered smooth if it needs to be approximated on a coarser grid to speed up convergence. Therefore an error is called smooth if it holds $Se \approx e$. The following section presents results on the smoothness properties of classical iterative methods such as the Jacobi or Gauß-Seidel methods. For the upcoming results the following inner products and norms need to be defined, with $u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$

$$\begin{aligned} (u, v) &= \sum_{i=1}^n u_i v_i, \\ (u, v)_0 &= (Du, v), & \|u\|_0 &= (u, u)_0^{1/2}, \\ (u, v)_1 &= (Au, v), & \|u\|_1 &= (u, u)_1^{1/2}, \\ (u, v)_2 &= (D^{-1}Au, Av), & \|u\|_2 &= (u, u)_2^{1/2}. \end{aligned}$$

It is now possible to define when an iterative method exhibits the smoothing property.

Definition 5.5 (Smoothing property). *A relaxation operator S satisfies the smoothing property with respect to a matrix A if*

$$\|Se\|_1^2 \leq \|e\|_1^2 - \sigma \|e\|_2^2$$

holds, with $\sigma > 0$ being independent of e .

It is evident that S is efficient in reducing the error as long as $\|e\|_2$ is relatively large compared to $\|e\|_1$. It can be proven that the Gauß-Seidel and the damped Jacobi method satisfy the smoothing property [27]. It is easy to see that a smooth error, which is characterized by $Se \approx e$ implies $\|e\|_2 \ll \|e\|_1$. For the residual, it holds

$$r = b - A\hat{x} = Ax - A\hat{x} = A(x - \hat{x}) = Ae,$$

i.e.,

$$(D^{-1}Ae, Ae) \ll (Ae, e) \Leftrightarrow (D^{-1}r, r) \ll (r, e),$$

which means that, on average, smooth errors are characterized by a scaled residual that is much smaller than the error. It follows that

$$a_{ii}^{-1}r_i^2 \ll |r_i e_i| \Leftrightarrow |r_i| \ll a_{ii}|e_i|,$$

therefore one can use the approximation given by

$$(5.3.1) \quad 0 \approx r_i = a_{ii}e_i + \sum_{j \in N_i} a_{i,j}e_j,$$

where e_i can be approximated locally as a function of its neighboring values e_j even if the error is globally large.

Definition 5.6 (Neighborhood of a variable). *Let Ω denote the index set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ of A . A variable $i \in \Omega$ is said to be (directly) coupled to a variable $j \in \Omega$ if $a_{i,j} \neq 0$. The (direct) neighborhood of a variable i is then defined by*

$$N_i := \{j \in \Omega : j \neq i, a_{i,j} \neq 0\}.$$

Additionally, the following notations are used

$$\begin{aligned} N_i^- &:= \{j \in N_i, a_{i,j} < 0\}, \\ N_i^+ &:= \{j \in N_i, a_{i,j} > 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

5.3.3 Grid Transfer

To implement the hierarchical approach of multigrid methods and utilize the coarse grid correction principle, it is necessary to define operators facilitating the transition between various grids. This will be elucidated in the following. If only one coarser grid is constructed, the coarse grid can be denoted by H and the fine grid by h . Therefore the system of equations on the fine grid can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{j \in \Omega_h} a_{i,j}^h e_j^h = r_i^h \quad (\forall i \in \Omega_h),$$

with Ω_h denoting the index set of level h . A coarse grid system can be derived by determining which variables are to be included at the coarse level and which are to remain at the fine level. Therefore Ω_h has to be split into disjoint subsets C and F . The set C contains all variables that are also present on the coarse level, and F contains all variables that are only present on the fine level. Therefore $\Omega_H = C$. The coarse grid system is then given by

$$\sum_{l \in \Omega_H} a_{k,l}^h e_l^H = r_k^H \quad (\forall k \in \Omega_H).$$

Under the assumption that such a splitting is given, the AMG system on the coarse level $A_H e_H = r_H$ is constructed based on the Galerkin principle

$$A_H := I_h^H A_h I_H^h,$$

with I_h^H being the restriction operator and I_H^h the interpolation operator. For more details about the Galerkin approach, see [30]. For symmetric positive definite matrices, the restriction is always defined as the transpose of the interpolation

$$I_h^H = (I_H^h)^\top.$$

It holds that A_H is again symmetric and positive definite, as long as I_H^h has full rank [27].

5.3.4 Restriction

The role of the restriction operator is to use matrix information to determine which variables should be included in the coarse set C and which should remain in the fine set F . First the standard restriction procedure is described. Afterwards a parallel coarsening scheme called *Parallel Modified Independent Set* (PMIS) is presented.

Definition 5.7 (Strong coupling). *A variable i is said to be strongly coupled to another variable j if*

$$-a_{i,j} \geq \epsilon_{str} \max_{a_{i,k} < 0} |a_{i,k}|$$

for a fixed $\epsilon_{str} \in (0, 1)$. The set of all strong couplings of i is denoted by

$$S_i := \{j \in N_i : i \text{ is strongly coupled to } j\}.$$

The set S_i^\top then consists of all variables j that are strongly coupled to i .

The variables to be included in the coarse set should be chosen based on the following criteria. Firstly, the number of C -variables, which are variables contained in the set C , should be less than the number of variables in the fine system. Moreover, it holds that when two variables are strongly coupled, they have a small relative error, therefore a

coarse grid correction of this error is not necessary, so it would be inefficient to select both nodes to be in the coarse set. It is important to note that every F -variable that is a variable within the F set should have a significant coupling to neighboring C -variables. This ensures that an F -variable receives sufficient information from the C -variables. Finally, the distribution of the C - and F -variables should be uniform throughout the matrix.

The standard restriction procedure operates as follows. First, a variable is chosen to become a C -variable. Then, all variables that are strongly coupled to this variable become F -variables. Next, another C -variable is chosen from the remaining ones, and again, their strongly coupled variables become F -variables. This procedure stops when all variables are either C - or F -variables. To achieve a uniform distribution over C - and F -variables, the C -variables must be chosen in a specific order. Therefore, a measure of importance is used to select the next C -variable in each step. The chosen variable is the one with the largest value for this measure. The measure of importance is defined as

$$\lambda_i := |S_i^\top \cap U| + 2|S_i^\top \cap F| \quad (i \in U).$$

U represents the current set of undecided variables. At the start, the measure λ is large for variables that have many strongly coupled F -variables. Later, the measure prefers to select C -variables on which many F -variables depend. It is stated that after the procedure, all F -variables have at least one strong coupling to a C -variable and none of the C -variables have a strong coupling to other C -variables. It should be noted that variables in the U set may not be strongly coupled to any of the C -variables. However, they are still strongly coupled to at least one F -variable, therefore they will be considered as F -variables. In interpolation these variables are indirectly interpolated through their strong F -couplings. In Figure 5.3.2, two examples for a coarsening procedure are presented.

Figure 5.3.2: Two examples of a coarsening procedure. The undecided points with the highest λ value are shown in bold-italics [30].

A parallel coarsening scheme called *Parallel Modified Independent Set* (PMIS) is introduced in [8]. PMIS was originally created to address memory and execution time

issues that may arise when solving three-dimensional problems. It is based solely on enforcing a maximum independent set property, resulting in sparser coarse grids than traditional coarsening schemes. The following is an explanation of the PMIS coarsening algorithm. First, an auxiliary strength matrix B is defined as

$$B_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i \neq j \text{ and } |a_{i,j}| \geq \beta \max_{k \neq i} |a_{i,k}|, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

with $\beta \in (0.25, 0.5)$. Therefore $B_{i,j}$ is only equal to one if i is strongly coupled to j and the i -th row of B defines $B_i = \{j \in A \mid B_{i,j} = 1\}$, the set of variables that couples i . By $B_i^\top = \{j \in A \mid B_{j,i} = 1\}$, the set of variables that are coupled by i is denoted. Then, an undirected graph is constructed, where the vertices V are the entries of the matrix A and the edges are defined as $E = \{\{i, j\} \in V \times V \mid B_{i,j} = 1 \text{ or } B_{j,i} = 1\}$. The maximum independent set of vertices is then searched for in the constructed graph. $I \subset V$ is an independent set if $\forall i, j \in I : \{i, j\} \notin E$. It is called a maximal independent set if I is an independent set and $\forall j \in V \setminus I, I \cup \{j\}$ is not an independent set.

Algorithm 5.3.1 PMIS

Require: $G = (V, E) = g(B)$, define weights $w(i)$ for all $i \in V$: $w(i) = \#B_i^\top + \text{Rand}([0, 1])$.

- 1: Initialize the set of F -points: $F = \{i \in V \mid \#B_i^\top = 0\}$.
 - 2: Initialize the set of C -points: $C = \emptyset$.
 - 3: Take the F -points out of the remaining vertex set: $V' = V \setminus F$.
 - 4: The subgraph induced by the remaining vertex set is then $G' = g(V', B)$.
 - 5: **while** $V' \neq \emptyset$ **do**
 - 6: Choose an independent set I of V' in G' :
 - 7: $i \in I$ if and only if $w(i) > w(j)$ for all j with $\{i, j\} \in E'$.
 - 8: Make all elements of I C -points: $C = C \cup I$.
 - 9: Make all elements of $V' \setminus I$ that are strongly coupled by a new C -point F -points:
 - 10: $F = F \cup F_{\text{new}}$, with $F_{\text{new}} = \{j \in V' \setminus I \mid \exists i \in I : i \in B_j\}$.
 - 11: Remove all new C - and F -points from V' : $V' = V' \setminus (I \cup F_{\text{new}})$.
 - 12: The remaining subgraph is then $G' = g(V', B)$.
 - 13: **end while**
-

The different steps in Algorithm 5.3.1 can be briefly described as follows:

1. Initially, variables in V that are not coupled by any other variable are designated as F -variables.
2. Each variable i in V is assigned a measure $w(i)$, calculated as the sum of the number of variables coupled by i , denoted as $\#B_i^\top$, and a random number between 0 and 1 ($\text{Rand}([0, 1])$). This measure determines a variable's eligibility to become a C -point. The addition of a random number breaks ties when the number of coupled variables of neighboring points is equal.

3. In each iteration, unassigned variables in V become C -variables if their measure is greater than that of their unassigned strongly connected neighbors. This process continues until all variables in the grid are partitioned into C - and F -variables.
4. The resulting set of C -variables forms a maximal independent set in the undirected graph of the auxiliary strength matrix B . This set is independent because each new C -variable has only F -variables as neighbors by construction. It is maximal because converting any F -variable to a C -variable would compromise independence, as every new F -variable is adjacent to a C -variable by construction.
5. When a new set of C -variables is determined, only unassigned neighbors that are strongly coupled by a new C -variable become F -variables. This ensures that all F -variables, except possibly the initially designated ones, are coupled by at least one C -variable, enabling them to interpolate effectively.

5.3.5 Interpolation

The objective of interpolation is to obtain a precise approximation of e_i with $i \in F$, by using information from the coarse grid. Therefore interpolation weights have to be computed such that

$$e_i = \sum_{j \in P_i} w_{i,j} e_j,$$

with $P_i \subseteq C$ the interpolatory variables. It is known from (5.3.1) that e_i is a good approximation if the error is smooth. The following describes different interpolation schemes.

In direct interpolation the interpolation set P_i for a variable $i \in F$ defined as

$$C_i^s := C \cap S_i.$$

Therefore e_i is interpolated from the variables in the coarse set that are neighbors of i and to which i is strongly coupled. Under the assumption that i has both positive and negative connections, which means $N_i^+ \neq \emptyset$ and $N_i^- \neq \emptyset$ the interpolation weights can be derived from (5.3.1),

$$(5.3.2) \quad a_{i,i} + \alpha_i \sum_{k \in P_i} a_{i,k}^- + \beta_i \sum_{k \in P_i} a_{i,k}^+ = 0,$$

with

$$(5.3.3) \quad \alpha_i = \frac{\sum_{k \in N_i} a_{i,k}^-}{\sum_{k \in P_i} a_{i,k}^-}, \quad \text{and} \quad \beta_i = \frac{\sum_{k \in N_i} a_{i,k}^+}{\sum_{k \in P_i} a_{i,k}^+}.$$

This results in interpolation weights

$$w_{i,k} = \begin{cases} -\alpha_i a_{i,k} / a_{ii}, & k \in P_i^-, \\ -\beta_i a_{i,k} / a_{ii}, & k \in P_i^+. \end{cases}$$

If either $N_i^+ = \emptyset$ or $N_i^- = \emptyset$, the definitions can be modified by setting $P_i^- = \emptyset$ and $\alpha_i = 0$ or $P_i^+ = \emptyset$ and $\beta_i = 0$.

In standard interpolation, the previously described direct interpolation is modified so that each variable's strong F -couplings are also indirectly included in the interpolation. Therefore for each $j \in F_i^s$ with $F_i^s = F \cap S_i$ being the set of all F -variables which are strongly coupled to j , e_j is replaced by

$$e_j \rightarrow - \sum_{k \in \hat{N}_j} a_{j,k} e_k / a_{j,j}.$$

such that e_j is eliminated by means of the corresponding j -th equations. This results in a new equation for e_i ,

$$(5.3.4) \quad e_i = \hat{a}_{i,i} e_i + \sum_{j \in \hat{N}_i} \hat{a}_{i,j} e_j = 0,$$

with $\hat{N}_i = \{j \neq i : \hat{a}_{i,j} \neq 0\}$.

In [9], it is stated that when using the PMIS coarsening scheme interpolation methods that only use distance-one neighbors like the direct interpolation, lead to non-scalable AMG convergence factors. For this reason, the use of so-called distance-two methods is recommended when using the PMIS method. An example for a distance-two interpolation method is the standard interpolation. Another method is the so-called *extended+i* interpolation, introduced in [9]. This interpolation scheme extends the direct interpolation formula by employing the interpolatory set utilized in the standard interpolation. This results in including C -variables that are distance-two away from a F -variable and deals efficiently with strong F - F connections that do not share a common C -variable. By adding one more modification that includes connections $a_{j,k}$ not only from strong, fine neighbors j of i to variables k of the interpolatory set but also connections $a_{j,i}$ to variable i itself, an efficient interpolation scheme is given which can be combined with the PMIS coarsening scheme. This leads to interpolation weights

$$w_{i,j} = \frac{1}{\tilde{a}_{i,i}} \left(a_{i,j} + \sum_{k \in F_i^s} a_{i,k} \frac{\bar{a}_{k,j}}{\sum_{l \in \hat{C}_i \cup \{i\}} \bar{a}_{k,l}} \right), \quad j \in \hat{C}_i,$$

with

$$\tilde{a}_{i,i} = a_{i,i} + \sum_{n \in D_i^w} a_{i,n} + \sum_{k \in F_i^s} a_{i,k} \frac{\bar{a}_{k,i}}{\sum_{l \in \hat{C}_i \cup \{i\}} \bar{a}_{k,l}},$$

where $\hat{C}_i = C_i \cup \bigcup_{j \in F_i^s} C_j$ and D_i^w being an appropriate set which is different for each operator.

5.3.6 AMG Algorithm

Now, the complete AMG method can be presented, which integrates all the components described earlier. The AMG algorithm has two phases. The first phase is the setup

phase, where coarse grid levels are chosen recursively and grid transfer operators are defined. The second phase is the solution phase, which utilizes the computed components from the setup phase to perform a multigrid cycle until a desired tolerance is achieved. Different cycle types are available to determine the movement through the hierarchy of the grids. For $\gamma = 1$ the V-cycle follows while $\gamma = 2$ determines the W-cycle. When using the V-cycle in each multigrid cycle call, the cycle is performed once, in contrast to the W-cycle where each call of the W-cycle creates two multigrid cycles. The hierarchy resulting from the different cycle types is illustrated in Figure 5.3.3. In Algorithm 5.3.2, the proceeding of the solution phase is presented, where the coarsest grid is denoted by $k = 0$ and k is the current level. The algorithm consists of the following steps.

1. Starting with an initial guess $x^{(0)}$, the chosen smoother is applied ν_1 times.
2. The residual is computed and restricted to the next coarser level.
3. If this next coarser level is the coarsest level, then the residual equation is solved directly. Otherwise, the residual equation is solved by another multigrid cycle, which will be applied γ times.
4. When the coarsest level is reached and a solution at this level is obtained, then this solution is interpolated back to the next finer grid, to update the initial guess, and then smoothed ν_2 times.

Algorithm 5.3.2 AMG

Require: Level k , cycle type γ , initial guess $x_k^{(0)}$, matrix A_k , right-hand side b_k , pre-smoothing steps ν_1 , post-smoothing steps ν_2

```

1: procedure MULTIGRIDCYCLE( $k, \gamma, x_k^{(0)}, A_k, b_k, \nu_1, \nu_2$ )
2:    $x_k \leftarrow x_k^{(0)}$ 
3:   for  $c = 1, \dots, \gamma$  do ▷ Run the cycle  $\gamma$  times
4:      $x_k \leftarrow \text{SMOOTH}_{\nu_1}(x_k, A_k, b_k)$  ▷ Apply  $\nu_1$  smoothing steps to  $x_k$ 
5:      $r_k \leftarrow b_k - A_k x_k$  ▷ Compute the residual
6:      $r_{k-1} \leftarrow I_k^{k-1} r_k$  ▷ Restrict the residual
7:     if  $k = 1$  then
8:       Solve  $A_{k-1} e_{k-1} = r_{k-1}$  exactly using a direct or fast iterative solver
9:     else
10:      Solve  $e_{k-1} \leftarrow \text{MULTIGRIDCYCLE}(k-1, \gamma, 0, A_{k-1}, r_{k-1}, \nu_1, \nu_2)$ 
11:    end if
12:     $e_k \leftarrow I_{k-1}^k e_{k-1}$  ▷ Interpolate the correction
13:     $x_k \leftarrow x_k + e_k$  ▷ Update the solution
14:  end for
15:   $x_k \leftarrow \text{SMOOTH}_{\nu_2}(x_k, A_k, b_k)$  ▷ Apply  $\nu_2$  smoothing steps to  $x$ 
16:  return  $x_k$  ▷ Return the updated solution
17: end procedure

```

Figure 5.3.3: On the left, the V-cycle hierarchy is shown, and on the right, the W-cycle hierarchy is shown for a 4-level method, taken from [30]. The white dot represents the coarse grid solver, while the black dot represents smoothing steps. The varying heights of the dots indicate the different levels, while the connections between the dots represent a restriction or interpolation step.

5.4 Preconditioning

Preconditioning is a technique that can improve both the efficiency and robustness of iterative methods. It involves transforming the linear system to be solved into an equivalent system that is easier and faster to solve. Therefore, consider the linear system of equations

$$(5.4.1) \quad Ax = b,$$

with $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $b \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The goal is to convert this system into another system that has the same solution but with spectral properties that are more beneficial for its system matrix

$$(5.4.2) \quad \tilde{A}x = \tilde{b}.$$

To obtain (5.4.2) from (5.4.1) a regular matrix M is used which is called the preconditioning matrix. There are different methods to precondition the system.

1. Left preconditioning $M^{-1}Ax = M^{-1}b$, $\tilde{A} = M^{-1}A$,
2. Right preconditioning $\begin{cases} AM^{-1}u = b, & \tilde{A} = AM^{-1}, \\ x = M^{-1}u, \end{cases}$
3. Split preconditioning $\begin{cases} M_1^{-1}AM_2^{-1}u = M_1^{-1}b, & \tilde{A} = M_1^{-1}AM_2^{-1}, \\ x = M_2^{-1}u. \end{cases}$

For split preconditioning the matrix has to be factorized, $M = M_1 \cdot M_2$.

5.4.1 AMG as a Preconditioner

AMG aims to capture all relevant influences through appropriate coarsening and interpolation. However, achieving optimal interpolation is rare, and reducing errors

can be less effective for specific error components. This can result in an AMG iteration matrix with a few eigenvalues being significantly closer to one than others. In such cases, the convergence of AMG may be slowed down by a few error components that converge slowly, while the majority converge rapidly. For this particular type of error, Krylov subspace methods are effective in efficiently eliminating the corresponding frequencies. As a result, AMG is commonly used not only as a standalone solver but also in combination with Krylov subspace methods to enhance robustness, as suggested in [30]. In this case, AMG is utilized as a preconditioner and has been proven to be effective.

5.4.2 Flexible GMRES

The GMRES method can be improved by using a preconditioner [23]. There are various options available, such as right, left and split preconditioning. These methods assume that the preconditioner matrix M is constant. In this work, we focus on a flexible variant of the preconditioned GMRES method, known as the flexible GMRES (FGMRES) method, where the preconditioner $M^{(k)}$ can change in each step. The main difference to

Algorithm 5.4.1 FGMRES

Require: Matrix A , right-hand side vector b , initial guess $x^{(0)}$, maximum iteration count m

- 1: Compute $r^{(0)} = b - Ax^{(0)}$, $\beta = \|r^{(0)}\|_2$, and $v^{(1)} = r^{(0)}/\beta$
 - 2: **for** $k = 1$ to m **do**
 - 3: Compute $z^{(k)} = (M^{(k)})^{-1}v^{(k)}$
 - 4: Compute $w^{(k)} = Az^{(k)}$
 - 5: **for** $i = 1$ to k **do**
 - 6: $h_{i,k} = (w^{(k)}, v^{(i)})$
 - 7: $w^{(k)} = w^{(k)} - h_{i,k}v^{(i)}$
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: Compute $h_{k+1,k} = \|w^{(k)}\|_2$ and $v^{(k+1)} = w^{(k)}/h_{k+1,k}$
 - 10: Define $Z^{(m)} = [z^{(1)}, \dots, z^{(m)}]$, $\bar{H}^{(m)} = \{h_{i,k}\}_{1 \leq i \leq k+1; 1 \leq k \leq m}$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: Compute $y^{(m)} = \arg \min_y \|\beta e_1 - \bar{H}^{(m)}y\|_2$, and $x^{(m)} = x^{(0)} + Z^{(m)}y^{(m)}$.
 - 13: **if** convergence criteria satisfied **then**
 - 14: Stop
 - 15: **else**
 - 16: Set $x^{(0)} \leftarrow x^{(m)}$ and GoTo 1
 - 17: **end if**
-

the usual GMRES algorithm is that the action $A(M^{(k)})^{-1}$ on a vector v of the Krylov subspace is no longer in the span of $V^{(k+1)}$. However, it holds

$$AZ^{(k)} = V^{(k+1)}\bar{H}^{(k)},$$

with $Z^{(k)} = [z^{(1)}, \dots, z^{(k)}]$ and $z^{(k)} = (M^{(k)})^{-1}v^{(k)}$. A proof of optimality similar to the one used to define GMRES can be provided. Therefore consider $z = x^{(0)} + Z^{(k)}y$ in the affine space $x^{(0)} + \text{span}(Z^{(k)})$. It can be shown that

$$J(y) = \|b - A(x^{(0)} + Z^{(k)}y)\|_2 = \|\beta e_1 - \bar{H}^{(k)}y\|_2$$

[23]. Since the algorithm minimizes this norm over all $u \in \mathbb{R}^k$ to achieve $y^{(k)}$, the approximate solution $x^{(k)} = x^{(0)} + Z^{(k)}y^{(k)}$ has the smallest residual norm in $x^{(0)} + \text{span}(Z^{(k)})$.

6 Numerical Experiments

This chapter presents experiments conducted to investigate the potential for improving the computational efficiency of the (probabilistic) label spreading algorithm. The primary goal is to develop an efficient solution to the linear system of equations (2.4.1) involved in label spreading. In addition, the time measurements for the entire label spreading algorithm for both deterministic and probabilistic labels are presented in order to identify potential areas for improving the efficiency of the computational process. The initial setting for the label spreading algorithm is explained, and then the settings for the methods used to solve the linear system of equations are presented. Finally, the hardware on which the experiments were performed is discussed. Subsequently, experiments are performed on different data sets, including both probabilistic and deterministic data.

6.1 Implementation Details

In the conducted experiments for the label spreading algorithm, the affinity matrix was constructed in accordance with the specifications outlined in (3.2.1). The parameter σ^2 , which is utilized in the construction of the affinity matrix, is selected to be the average of the squared distances across all data points in the graph to their respective k -nearest neighbors. In the context of the label spreading for deterministic labels, $n_{samples}$ is set to $n_{classes} \cdot 5$, and the number of labeled data points in each class is set to five. In the application of probabilistic labels, different numbers of $n_{samples}$ are considered.

To determine the most efficient method for solving the linear system of equations, a comparison is made between the following methods: the conjugate gradient method (CG) 5.2.2 implemented with SciPy [31], the solution by a direct solver of SciPy using the `spsolve` function, implementations of CG and algebraic multigrid (AMG) 5.3 of the AmgX library from NVIDIA [17]. The AmgX library is a GPU-accelerated core solver library. In order to facilitate easier access to the library, a Python interface [26] was employed. Furthermore, the potential use of AMG as a preconditioner in FGMRES is considered. This involves performing one V-cycle iteration and setting the initial Krylov subspace size to 20. In light of the aforementioned considerations, this method shall henceforth be designated as FGMRES+AMG. When using iterative methods to solve the linear equation system, these are executed until the relative residual norm is less than 10^{-12} . In the context of solving the linear system of equations with algebraic multigrid methods, the method for determining the C - and F -variables is fixed to the PMIS algorithm with $\beta = 0.25$, as outlined in Algorithm 5.3.1, and the interpolation scheme is fixed to be the *extended+i* method. In order to solve the linear system of

equations at the coarsest level, a dense LU solver is chosen. The number of smoothing steps is set to 1 for both ν_1 and ν_2 .

Given the hardware configuration, the experiments were conducted using the NVIDIA Quadro P6000 GPU with 24 GB of memory and two Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6138 CPUs with 2.00 GHz and 20 cores/40 threads with 502 GB of RAM. Consequently, when utilising SciPy and the AmgX library, performance is evaluated by comparing two 20-core CPUs with SciPy and one GPU with the AmgX library.

6.2 Two Moons

In this section, experiments are conducted on the toy data set *Two Moons* [20], which consists of two intertwining half moons that cannot be linearly separated. The number of data points used to generate the data set and the degree of noise present in the distribution of the moons can be determined. When a minimal noise parameter is utilized, the moons can be clearly distinguished from one another. However, as the noise parameter increases, the distinction between them becomes increasingly challenging. In conducting the experiments, the noise parameter was fixed at a value of 0.1, which was selected to achieve a good separation of the moons, thus fulfilling the cluster and smoothness assumptions of semi-supervised learning.

Figure 6.2.1: *Two Moons* dataset generated with 1,000 data points and noise set to 0.1.

6.2.1 Setup for AMG

The initial experiment involves selecting the remaining free components of the algebraic multigrid method. Therefore, the *Two Moons* dataset, comprising 1,000,000 data points, is used with label spreading applied to this data with $\alpha = 0.99$ and the number of nearest neighbors k is set to 20. The value of the parameter $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ was selected for two reasons. First, it was also selected in reference to the work of [33] to test the effectiveness of the label spreading method for classification tasks. Second, it will become evident later that a value of α close to 1 is of practical relevance, as the intensity must be high for the spreading of labels on large datasets. Subsequently, the smoother and the number of levels were analyzed, with the V-cycle being selected as the algebraic multigrid cycle type. Other types, such as W- and K-cycles, were also considered, but did not result in superior performance outcomes and are therefore not presented. The objective is to identify the setting that enables the most efficient solution to the linear system (2.4.1) using the AMG method when one class is spreaded. It is crucial to highlight that the duration of the solution phase is of greater relevance than that of the setup phase. This is because in the label spreading algorithm, the linear system of equations must be solved $n_{classes}$ times, whereas the setup phase is only required to be conducted once, as the matrix remains unchanged. Table 6.2.1 shows the results of a comparison of the different components.

Component	Method	Setup time	Solve time	Iter	Time per iter
Smoother	Block-Jacobi	0.43s	1.11s	30	0.04s
	Multicolor GS	0.48s	0.86s	20	0.04s
# Levels	3	5.70s	0.95s	20	0.05s
	4	0.51s	0.85s	20	0.04s
	5	0.48s	0.85s	20	0.04s
	6	0.48s	0.86s	20	0.04s

Table 6.2.1: A comparative analysis of the various components of the AMG method. The time required for the solution phase, as well as the setup phase, the number of iterations, and the time per iteration are all compared.

In the initial step, the smoother is selected, while six constructed levels, including the fine level system, are fixed. The smoothers that yielded particularly noteworthy outcomes were the Block-Jacobi and Multicolor Gauß-Seidel smoother. Their results are presented herewith. In addition to these smoothers, the conjugate gradient method and a diagonal incomplete LU solver were also considered as smoothers. However, their performance was not deemed satisfactory. Table 6.2.1 indicates that the Block-Jacobi smoother is slightly faster than the Multicolor Gauß-Seidel smoother in the time required for the setup phase. However, the iteration count and time for the solution phase of the Multicolor Gauß-Seidel smoother is lower. Consequently, the smoother is set to be Multicolor Gauß-Seidel, as the improvement resulting from lower iteration counts and less time for the solution

phase is more beneficial. The number of coarse grid levels to be constructed can now be selected, where level one is defined as the fine level system. Table 6.2.2 presents the dimension of the system matrix at a given level. Table 6.2.1 contains corresponding time measurements. A notable reduction in the time required for the setup and solution phases is evident, from allowing four instead of three coarse levels. Further enhancements can be observed by allowing five coarse levels. The introduction of six levels results in a slight increase in the time required for the solution phase, but also in a further enhancement for the setup phase. It is important to note that the number of levels to construct depends on the size of the matrix as well as the number of nearest neighbors. The choice of the number of nearest neighbors directly affects the coarsening procedure, since the nearest neighbors of a variable i correspond to the neighborhood as described in Definition 5.6. Therefore, an increasing number of nearest neighbors results in stronger coarsening, so that fewer coarse levels need to be constructed. Consequently, it is essential to select an appropriate number of levels for each matrix size and number of nearest neighbors separately. When conducting experiments on 1,000,000 data points and at least 20 nearest neighbors, the maximum number of levels that can be constructed is set to five. In the event that a smaller number of nearest neighbors or more data points are utilized, it is determined that the coarsening procedure should terminate the generation of coarser levels if the number of unknowns of the next coarser level would be less than 128.

Level	Number of unknowns
1	1000000
2	88839
3	13052
4	2016
5	537
6	170

Table 6.2.2: The number of unknowns at different coarse levels is presented.

6.2.2 The Impact of Label Spreading Parameters on the Performance of Different Solvers

Having established the components for AMG, the subsequent step is to analyse the performance of various solvers on the linear system of equations associated with the label spreading algorithm. This analysis will focus on different parameters of the label spreading method. The solvers to be compared are those described in Section 6.1.

Effect of α

The performance of the different solvers is initially evaluated for distinct values of $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, the remaining parameters for label spreading and the proceeding to compare the performance are identical to those outlined in Section 6.2.1. As previously stated

in Section 2.4.3, the value of α influences the condition number of the linear system of equations. Consequently in Table 6.2.3, the values of α are selected in such a manner that one α results in a relatively low condition number of the system matrix, and another α yields a higher condition number.

α	Solver	Setup time	Solve time	Iter
0.6	<code>spsolve</code> (SciPy)	/	472.56s	/
	CG (SciPy)	/	3.63s	21
	CG (AmgX)	0.00s	0.18s	21
	AMG	0.50s	0.45s	10
	FGMRES+AMG	0.50s	0.44s	8
0.99	<code>spsolve</code> (SciPy)	/	481.71s	/
	CG (SciPy)	/	20.12s	167
	CG (AmgX)	0.00s	1.44s	167
	AMG	0.48s	0.86s	20
	FGMRES+AMG	0.48s	0.69s	13

Table 6.2.3: Comparison of the performance of different solvers for solving the linear system of equation of the label spreading algorithm with $k = 20$, $n_{data} = 1,000,000$.

Table 6.2.3 demonstrates that the iterative methods result in a notable acceleration in the solution time of the system of equations. This performance can be further enhanced by using the AmgX library-based methods, which require less computation time than the SciPy implementation. It is important to highlight that the use of AmgX library-based methods can significantly reduce the time required to solve a linear system. This reduction in time can be substantial; in fact, it can be reduced to less than one second. This is in contrast to the time required to solve the linear system directly, which can be over seven minutes. When comparing the iterative methods, CG exhibits superior performance for α values of 0.6, while the AMG demonstrate enhanced performance for α values of 0.99. Consequently, CG is more effective when low spreading intensity is required, whereas AMG is preferable when high spreading intensity is desired. When the setup phase is considered alongside the solution phase when using FGMRES+AMG, it can be demonstrated that the total time required is still smaller than if CG were used instead. The number of iterations of the algebraic multigrid methods is considerably lower than that of the conjugate gradient method. This is true for both values of α . This indicates that label spreading is more feasible due to the hierarchical structure of AMG. However, this topic will be further discussed in Section 6.2.3. The performance of AMG can be further enhanced by utilizing it as a preconditioner in the FGMRES+AMG method, which leads to a reduction in the number of iterations and overall computation time. In order to gain a more detailed understanding of the impact of α on the time required for the solution phase, Figure 6.2.2 illustrates the effect of different α values on the solution phase and the number of iterations needed for CG

and FGMRES+AMG. As the value of α increases, which results in an increase in the condition number, the number of iterations and time required for the solution phase increase for both methods. Consequently, the course of the graphs is similar to the course of the condition number. Nevertheless, FGMRES+AMG requires a significantly smaller number of iterations than CG for all values of α . Given that the time required for one iteration of CG is considerably less expensive than that of FGMRES+AMG, CG is faster if the difference in the iteration counts of CG and FGMRES+AMG is not too large. Additionally, it can be observed that from a value of $\alpha \approx 0.95$, FGMRES+AMG becomes faster than CG. From this, it can be inferred that the optimal choice between CG and FGMRES+AMG is contingent upon the value of α . It should be noted that for the AmgX implementation in the context of CG, a time is provided for the setup phase. However, this is of a negligible nature, as the phase itself does not include any calculations.

(a) Number of iterations for different values of α . (b) Time of the solution phase for different values of α .

Figure 6.2.2: Impact of the parameter α on the iteration number and solution time for CG and FGMRES+AMG.

Effect of n_{data}

Another factor that affects the performance of different solvers is the problem size, which is equivalent to the number of data points n_{data} . Therefore, this study analyzes how solvers perform for different numbers of data points for $\alpha = 0.6$ and $\alpha = 0.99$. The number of nearest neighbors is set to $k = 20$. The total number of analyzed data points reached five million. It should be noted that the methods implemented with the AmgX library permit the solution of linear systems of equations with high numbers of unknown variables up to 20 million. However, the memory capacity of the GPU was exceeded when numbers of unknown variables of 50 million were tested.

Figure 6.2.3 illustrates that as the number of data points increases, the execution time and the number of iterations for all methods analyzed exhibit a linear increase. Consequently, it is of paramount importance to employ the most optimal method for

solving the system of equations pertaining to large datasets, with the objective of ensuring optimal computational efficiency. This also indicates that the condition number of the matrix does depend on α , rather than the number of data points. This entails the utilization of the CG method with an α of 0.6 and the FGMRES+AMG method with $\alpha = 0.99$. Therefore, the selection of the solver should not be contingent upon the number of data points, but rather upon the value of α , as previously outlined. Nevertheless, there is a correlation between the number of data points in a dataset and the value of α . For small datasets, a smaller value of α is sufficient to spread information, as the feature space is sparsely populated and therefore the graph (X, E, W) has fewer nodes and therefore the distance over which it is spread is shorter. In contrast, for large datasets, a value of α close to 1 is necessary, as in this case the graph has more nodes, the feature space is more densely populated, and therefore a strong spreading intensity is required to spread information over the entire graph. Additionally, it can be observed that while AMG and FGMRES+AMG perform almost equally for $\alpha = 0.6$, FGMRES+AMG achieves a significant improvement for $\alpha = 0.99$. Therefore, the use of AMG as a preconditioner in the FGMRES+AMG method should be preferred over AMG as a standalone solver. Moreover, it can be observed that the utilization of methods implemented based on the AmgX library is advantageous for any size of the dataset, in comparison to the SciPy implementation.

(a) Time of the solution phase for $\alpha = 0.6$. (b) Time of the solution phase for $\alpha = 0.99$.

Figure 6.2.3: Impact of n_{data} .

Effect of k -nearest neighbors

The final parameter to be considered is the effect of the number of nearest neighbors. Therefore, we again utilize the settings outlined in Section 6.2.1 and compare the performance of the solvers for different values of nearest neighbors. The results can be analyzed based on Table 6.2.4. It can be observed that an increasing number of nearest neighbors is associated with longer setup times at FGMRES+AMG, as well as with longer solution times for both CG and FGMRES+AMG. A positive aspect of using

more nearest neighbors is that the number of iterations decreases slightly. This finding aligns with theoretical predictions that posit that as the number of nearest neighbors increases, the matrix becomes denser, necessitating greater computational effort. It is also noteworthy that CG and AMG methods are efficient for sparse linear systems of equations, which motivates the use of a small number of nearest neighbors. Consequently, the number of nearest neighbors regarding the efficiency of the label spreading algorithm should be selected in a manner that minimizes the number of neighbors. However, the consequences on the accuracy of label spreading should also be considered. This topic will be further explored in Section 6.2.3. Table 6.2.5 presents the size of the coarse level matrices on different levels, constructed for varying numbers of nearest neighbors. It can be observed that as the number of nearest neighbors increases, coarsening becomes more intensive, necessitating the construction of fewer coarse levels. However, this does not result in faster setup or solution times for FGMRES+AMG.

α	Solver	k	Setup time	Solve time	Iter
0.6	CG (AmgX)	10	0.00s	0.10s	22
	CG (AmgX)	50	0.00s	0.47s	20
	CG (AmgX)	100	0.00s	1.01s	19
	FGMRES+AMG	20	0.23s	0.28s	8
	FGMRES+AMG	50	2.18s	1.02s	8
	FGMRES+AMG	100	7.89s	1.87s	7
0.99	CG (AmgX)	10	0.00s	0.76s	176
	CG (AmgX)	50	0.00s	3.79s	163
	CG (AmgX)	100	0.00s	8.80s	165
	FGMRES+AMG	20	0.22s	0.51s	15
	FGMRES+AMG	50	2.16s	1.75s	14
	FGMRES+AMG	100	7.89s	3.42s	13

Table 6.2.4: Comparison of the performance of different solvers for solving the linear system of the label spreading algorithm for different numbers of nearest neighbors, with $n_{data} = 1,000,000$.

Level	$k = 10$	$k = 10$	$k = 10$
1	1000000	1000000	1000000
2	148161	42949	24365
3	33583	6900	3930
4	7207	942	541
5	2049	252	145
6	633	/	/
7	228	/	/

Table 6.2.5: Number of unknowns for different coarse levels and for different numbers of nearest neighbors, when $\alpha = 0.99$.

6.2.3 Classification Accuracy of Label Spreading

This section examines the classification accuracy of the label spreading algorithm, with particular focus on the parameters α and the number of nearest neighbors. The objective is to identify the optimal values for these parameters that result in the highest levels of accuracy for the *Two Moons* dataset with 1,000,000 data points and a noise parameter of 0.1. Additionally, the influence of the solver on the accuracy of the label spreading algorithm is analyzed. Finally, the performance of the solvers on the optimal parameters in label spreading is evaluated. In order to quantify the classification accuracy of the label spreading algorithm, the proportion of correctly labeled data in the total number of data points is considered. Therefore, if y_i denotes the label of a data point x_i predicted by label spreading and l_i denotes the true label, the classification accuracy is given by

$$\frac{1}{n_{data}} \cdot \sum_{i=1, \dots, n_{data}} \mathbf{1}_{\{y_i=l_i\}}.$$

In order to ascertain the optimal parameter for attaining the highest possible accuracy, Figure 6.2.4 illustrates the impact of α on the classification accuracy for varying values of nearest neighbors. The parameter α controls the extent to which information is disseminated between data points, while the number of nearest neighbors controls the connectivity of the data points. A low value of nearest neighbors results in longer paths between data points that are not in each other's nearest neighbors. This leads to a reduction in the spread of information between those points. To solve the linear system of equations, the FGMRES+AMG method was employed. As illustrated, the highest classification accuracy is achieved with 100 nearest neighbors and $\alpha = 0.999$. With an increasing value of α , the accuracy increases for all values of nearest neighbors, with the exception of a narrow range where α is close to 1, where slight fluctuations can be observed. Additionally, an increasing number of neighbors results in higher classification accuracy. This is due to the fact that in a dataset comprising 1,000,000 data points, it is necessary to disseminate information widely in order for each data point to receive input from the labelled instances. The process of disseminating information widely is favored

by values of α close to 1 and a large number of nearest neighbors. Therefore, there exists a tradeoff between computational efficiency and dissemination, as high values for α and a large number of nearest neighbors result in increased computation time. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the method should be the primary focus, and an efficient solver should be employed for the given parameters in order to achieve the highest accuracy. Furthermore, it is crucial to acknowledge that an insufficient number of nearest neighbors may result in the formation of several connected components in the graph (X, E, W) , thereby hindering the effective dissemination of labels throughout the entire graph. This should be avoided, as the information from a labeled data point may not be distributed throughout the entire graph.

Figure 6.2.4: Classification accuracy for the *Two Moons* dataset for different values of α and numbers of nearest neighbors.

The subsequent step is to examine the impact of the solver employed for the linear equation system on the classification accuracy of label spreading. In order to ascertain which of these methods is more time-efficient and requires fewer iterations to attain a given level of accuracy, a comparison is made between CG and FGMRES+AMG in terms of the required elapsed time for the solution phase and the number of iterations required to achieve a specific tolerance for the relative residual norm. The corresponding achieved classification accuracy is then evaluated. The tolerance level for the relative residual norm is analyzed between 10^{-1} and 10^{-12} . The parameters of label spreading are set to the optimal values that were previously determined.

(a) Number of iterations performed and the achieved degree of classification accuracy. (b) Time of the solution phase and the achieved degree of classification accuracy.

Figure 6.2.5: Impact of the solver on the classification accuracy for $\alpha = 0.999$.

The results are presented in Figure 6.2.5. The visualization was also examined with a different scaling of the y-axis of the plot in order to be able to analyze more precisely how the graph behaves at the maximum classification accuracy of 99% achieved. However, this did not provide any additional insight. It can be observed that the selection of the solver has a significant impact on the classification accuracy. CG requires a greater number of iterations to achieve a high level of accuracy, whereas FGMRES+AMG can achieve the same level of accuracy in a single iteration. Furthermore, the time required for the solution phase to spread one class is also lower for FGMRES+AMG. Consequently, the time required for the label spreading algorithm could be further reduced by limiting the number of iterations to the number required to achieve the highest accuracy or by restricting the precision of the solve to 10^{-1} . However, it should be noted that this iteration count would have to be determined for each set of label spreading parameters and each dataset. In order to restrict the precision of the solve while maintaining the same classification accuracy, it is necessary to ensure that the optimal parameters for label spreading are employed. It is also important to highlight that when the optimal parameters for label spreading are not employed, it may result in the inability to achieve the highest level of classification accuracy when solving with FGMRES+AMG when CG is employed, as illustrated in Figure 6.2.6. Consequently, in order to guarantee optimal classification accuracy without the necessity of studying each parameter individually, the solver FGMRES+AMG is the optimal choice. The results also align with the assumption that AMG is more suitable for label spreading due to its hierarchical structure. The hypothesis is that, given the hierarchical structure of AMG, data points situated at a greater distance from those that have been labeled will receive more information when compared to if a similar process had been carried out using CG. This is because the reduction in the size of the graph resulting from the efficient utilisation of nearest neighbor dependency enables the construction of coarser levels where information can be distributed more widely. Furthermore, without the

necessity of solving the system of equations at that scale, the data points at the fine scale also gain information by interpolation.

(a) Number of iterations performed compared to the achieved degree of classification accuracy. (b) Time required for the solution phase compared to the achieved degree of accuracy.

Figure 6.2.6: Impact of the solver on the classification accuracy for $\alpha=0.9$.

In conclusion, the results of these studies indicate that FGMRES+AMG is the optimal solver for the linear equation system associated with label spreading. It is capable of providing the greatest classification accuracy while also minimizing computation time.

6.2.4 Time Measurements of Label Spreading

In order to complete the experiments on the *Two Moons* dataset, the computation time of the entire label spreading algorithm will now be examined on this data set. For this purpose, the label spreading parameters as described in Section 6.2.3 are used and the algorithm is applied to the *Two Moons* dataset with 1,000,000 data points and a noise parameter of 0.1. Of particular interest for time measurements are the following steps of label spreading, which are considered in more detail:

1. **NN-Search:** The calculation of the nearest neighbors of each data point. For the nearest neighbors search, the *NearestNeighbors* class from the *scikit-learn* library is utilized, configured to use the *ball tree* algorithm [19].
2. **Setup:** The setup phase for AmgX-based solvers, which involves the construction of coarser levels.
3. **Solve:** The solution phase for solving (2.4.1). Therefore solving the linear system of equation $n_{classes}$ -times.
4. **Setup+Solve:** The setup and solution phases, considered together, including the timing of data transmission to the GPU and subsequent reloading when using AmgX-based solvers.

5. **Label spreading:** The algorithmic approach to label spreading, which includes steps 1-4 and the calculation of the classification accuracy.

It should be noted that smaller calculations conducted during the algorithm are not displayed. However, their respective computation times are incorporated into the total calculation time in step *Label spreading*. Table 6.2.6 presents the outcomes of the time measurements, wherein the classification accuracy achieved by all solvers exhibited an identical outcome, reaching 99%. As can be observed, the primary component of the algorithm is the solution of the linear equation system. This component can be significantly reduced by utilizing the AmgX library-based methods. Consequently, instead of the nearly 10 minutes required by the SciPy implementation of CG, only approximately one minute is necessary when employing the AmgX library-based method, and even only 20 seconds when utilizing FGMRES+AMG. This implies that the total time required for the label spreading algorithm is considerably reduced, from approximately 12 minutes to 2.5 minutes when utilizing FGMRES+AMG. Consequently, the FGMRES+AMG approach represents an effective methodology for accelerating the label spreading algorithm.

Step:	CG (SciPy)	CG (AmgX)	FGMRES+AMG
NN-Search	108.45s	108.49s	108.81s
Setup	0.00s	0.03s	7.91s
Solve	590.24s	57.34s	11.62s
Setup+Solve	590.24s	58.34s	20.67s
Label spreading	717.99s	186.03s	148.59s

Table 6.2.6: Computation time required to execute the steps of the label spreading algorithm for the *Two Moons* dataset.

6.3 EMNIST-Digits

The next experiments will be conducted on an image classification dataset, the EMNIST-Digits dataset [6], with the objective of analyzing the performance of label spreading and different solvers. The Extended MNIST (EMNIST) dataset is an extension of the MNIST dataset [14]. Like MNIST, EMNIST was derived from a larger dataset, the NIST Special Database 19 [10], but follows the same conversion paradigm as MNIST. In this study, we focus on a subset of the EMNIST dataset, the EMNIST-Digits dataset. The dataset comprises 280,000 images of handwritten numbers, with a resolution of 28x28 pixels. The classes, which represent the numbers from 0 to 9, are balanced. Figure 6.3.1 presents a sample of the images in the dataset. Further insight into the dataset can be obtained from [6].

Figure 6.3.1: Four sample images from the EMNIST-Digits dataset.

6.3.1 Dimensionality Reduction for Image Data

As previously stated, the data in the EMNIST-Digits dataset comprises images with dimensions of 784. Therefore, a dimensionality reduction method should be applied initially to ensure local consistency in label spreading. The selected dimensionality reduction method should be that for which label spreading can achieve the highest classification accuracy. Furthermore, from an efficiency standpoint, applying a dimension reduction method is advantageous for the label spreading algorithm.

Method	Dimension	Dimensionality reduction	Nearest neighbors
None	784	0.00s	88,368.15s
CLIP	512	2,561.95s	56,676.61s
UMAP	50	611.26s	134.91s
PCA	50	241.55s	10,508.01s
CLIP+UMAP	50	2,877.42s	248.49s
CLIP+PCA	50	2,580.96s	10,860.66s

Table 6.3.1: Comparison of different dimensionality reduction methods in terms of computation time

As illustrated in Table 6.3.1, the construction of the affinity matrix, which involves determining the nearest neighbors of each data point, depends on both the dimension of the data and the dimensionality reduction method. It should be noted that the dimension of the lower dimensional space can also be chosen. The lower dimension should be selected in a manner that ensures the local consistency assumption is fulfilled, while also allowing for the retention of all relevant image features and the ability to capture the data's underlying structure. For the purposes of visualization in Figures 6.3.2 and 6.3.3, a subset of 1,000 data points was reduced to a two-dimensional representation in order to illustrate the potential differences in performance when mapping the data into a lower-dimensional subspace.

Figure 6.3.2: EMNIST-Digits data with data dimension reduced to two by UMAP.

Figure 6.3.3: EMNIST-Digits data with data dimension reduced to two by PCA.

It can be observed that when Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) 4.3 is employed, the data is effectively separated into distinct clusters for each class. Only a few datapoints are found within a cluster that does not correspond to their classification. In contrast, when the data points are reduced with Principle Component Analysis (PCA) 4.1, they are grouped together in a large cluster. Only those areas within the cluster in which points of the same class are found more frequently can be identified. Consequently, the cluster assumption of semi-supervised learning would not be fulfilled, which could result in lower classification accuracy results when using label

spreading. In the experiments presented in this section, the number of nearest neighbors as well as the lower dimension when reducing the data with PCA or UMAP was set to 50. This was done to ensure that the structure of the data could be captured, as even when the results obtained with UMAP for dimension two appeared satisfactory, some points were incorrectly clustered. The time required to reduce the dimensionality of the data is now considered. PCA was found to be the fastest method for reducing dimensions, followed by UMAP. However, significantly more time was required to reduce the data with Contrastive Language-Image Pre-Training (CLIP) 4.4, and the time required was correspondingly greater if PCA or UMAP was used in addition to CLIP. When considering the time required to calculate the nearest neighbors, it is evident that the greatest efficiency can be achieved by reducing the data with UMAP. However, when CLIP is used upstream, the calculation takes almost twice as long. Furthermore, to calculate the nearest neighbors on the data reduced with the other dimension reduction methods, significantly more time is required. This can be because of different reasons. One reason is the higher dimension when only reducing the data with CLIP. Another potential reason for the observed differences in computation time is that UMAP appears to embed the data more effectively into a lower-dimensional space than PCA.

(a) Comparison of dimensionality reduction methods without preprocessing the data with CLIP. (b) Comparison of dimensionality reduction methods with preprocessing the data with CLIP.

Figure 6.3.4: Impact of the dimensionality reduction methods on the classification accuracy.

Figure 6.3.4 illustrates that UMAP exhibits superior performance when $\alpha = 0.999$, outperforming all other methods and the baseline without dimension reduction in terms of optimal classification accuracy. It can be observed that the use of UMAP or PCA can enhance the classification accuracy for all values of α in comparison to the use of no dimension reduction method. The use of CLIP or CLIP in conjunction with UMAP or PCA resulted in enhanced classification accuracies for low values of α . However, this improvement was not observed when α was increased. In contrast, the utilization of CLIP did not result in any enhancement in classification accuracy for high α -values.

Furthermore, it was unable to achieve the highest possible accuracy observed when employing UMAP. It is important to note that the time required to solve the linear equation system with FGMRES+AMG appears to vary depending on the chosen dimension reduction method. Consequently, the use of UMAP enables the rapid attainment of solution times. When no dimension reduction method or PCA was employed, the time required for matrix setup and solution phase increased significantly, as illustrated in Table 6.3.2. Since the highest classification accuracy can also be achieved with

Method	Dimension	Setup	Solve
None	784	49.82s	145.06s
UMAP	50	0.62s	3.82s
PCA	50	42.01s	118.74s

Table 6.3.2: Effect of the dimension reduction method on the setup and solution phase for FGMRES+AMG.

UMAP, this may indicate that UMAP embeds the data in a highly efficient way so that label propagation works effectively and the construction of coarser layers is more efficient. This indicates that an embedding in which the label spreading algorithm is effective corresponds to a linear system of equations that can be solved efficiently by FGMRES+AMG. Consequently, in the subsequent experiments, the dimensionality reduction method is set to UMAP. However, in future work, it may be of interest to analyze the effect of the embedding of the data on the setup and solution phase of AMG.

6.3.2 Efficiency

The objective of this study is to investigate the time required to achieve a high classification accuracy when label spreading is employed. To this end, we will compare the classification accuracy that can be achieved and the time required if only five images per class are labeled by hand from the 280,000 images in the EMNIST-Digits dataset. In comparison to the steps of the label spreading algorithm outlined in Section 6.2.4, an additional preprocessing step is required. This is the time required to embed the dataset into a lower-dimensional subspace. As illustrated in Table 6.3.3, the utilization of the AmgX library-based solution can markedly diminish the time required to solve the linear system of equations. The FGMRES+AMG solver demonstrates superior performance compared to the CG solver, as illustrated in Figure 6.3.5, where the elapsed time for the solution phase and the number of iterations required to achieve a specific tolerance for the relative residual norm in comparison to the achieved classification accuracy are analyzed. Similar to the *Two Moons* dataset, FGMRES+AMG necessitates a single iteration to achieve the optimal accuracy, and it is more efficient than CG in terms of time. The step that requires the greatest amount of time is now the process of embedding the data in a low-dimensional subspace. However, this is a crucial step for the rapid

calculation of the nearest neighbors and the achievement of a high classification accuracy. A comparison of the time required to calculate the nearest neighbors on the EMNIST-Digits data, with a dimension of 50, to that of the *Two Moons* data, with a dimension of 2, reveals that the time required to calculate the nearest neighbors has increased only slightly in comparison to the increase in dimension. In future work, an investigation into the development of a more efficient method for calculating the nearest neighbors could be undertaken.

Step:	CG (SciPy)	CG (AmgX)	FGMRES+AMG
Reduction	611.26s	611.26s	611.26s
NN-Search	134.91s	134.91s	134.91s
Setup	0.00s	0.00s	0.62s
Solve	279.58s	7.30s	3.82s
Setup+Solve	279.58s	8.06s	5.38s
Label spreading	417.06s	145.54s	142.86s

Table 6.3.3: The classification accuracy that could be achieved is 98% for $\alpha=0.999$. For the duration of the entire label spreading algorithm, the time for dimensionality reduction is not included but considered to be preprocessing.

(a) Number of iterations performed compared to the achieved degree of accuracy. (b) Time of the solution phase compared to the achieved degree of accuracy.

Figure 6.3.5: Impact of the solver on the classification accuracy for $\alpha=0.999$ for the EMNIST-Digits dataset.

In conclusion, the results demonstrate that the time required for label spreading and achieving a classification accuracy of 98% could be reduced to less than three minutes when using FGMRES+AMG. This represents a notable enhancement when compared to the seven minutes required when using CG implemented with SciPy. Nevertheless, the most significant finding is that label spreading enables the rapid and accurate

classification of large datasets, even when only 50 images are labeled. This is a highly valuable outcome, as manually labeling the 280,000 images would be prohibitively costly and time-consuming.

6.3.3 EMNIST-Digits Extended

In order to further analyze the performance of label spreading on large datasets, we consider an extension of the EMNIST-Digits dataset in this section. For this purpose, the EMNIST-Digits dataset was extended to 1,000,000 images by augmenting the original 280,000 images. The augmentation included rotations of 15 degrees and shifts of up to three pixels vertically and horizontally. To reduce the dimensionality of the data, UMAP was employed, trained on both the original and augmented data. The parameters used for label spreading were the same as those described in Section 6.3. As experiments have shown, the value of α is again the optimal one. The highest classification accuracy that could be achieved in this experiment was 95% when labeling five images per class. The time required for each step of label spreading has increased in proportion to the number of data points, in comparison to the original EMNIST-Digits dataset. The shortest time required for label spreading was approximately 26.5 minutes, using FGMRES+AMG. The necessity for the utilization of an efficient solver for the linear system of equations is highlighted in this instance. To illustrate this point, consider the SciPy implementation of CG, which would necessitate approximately 22 minutes to solve (2.4.1). In contrast, the FGMRES+AMG approach would take about half a minute, as shown by the data presented in Table 6.3.4. Once again, it was demonstrated that employing label spreading in conjunction with an FGMRES+AMG solver is an effective approach for achieving high classification accuracy with a relatively modest quantity of hand-labeled data.

Step:	CG (SciPy)	CG (AmdX)	FGMRES+AMG
Reduction	3,671.21s	3,671.21s	3,671.21s
NN-Search	1,539.29s	1,539.29s	1,539.29s
Setup	0.00s	0.00s	3.22s
Solve	1,278.93s	82.27s	27.89s
Setup+Solve	1,278.93s	82.27s	32.16s
Label spreading	2,837.73s	1,641.07s	1,590.96s

Table 6.3.4: The classification accuracy that could be achieved is 95% for $\alpha=0.999$. For the duration of the entire label spreading algorithm, the time to reduce the dimension is not included but considered to be preprocessing.

The extended EMNIST-Digits dataset permits the examination of the influence of the number of data points on the duration of the solution phase for distinct solvers, also for the EMNIST-Digits dataset. Figure 6.3.6 illustrates that the time required for the solution phase appears to be linearly proportional to the number of data points for all

solvers and values of α . The investigation yielded the following findings: in the context of large datasets, FGMRES+AMG is the most effective solver when the value of α is close to 1. This is of practical relevance, as the α parameter is typically required to be close to 1 in the case of such large datasets to be able to disseminate information widely. In the case of smaller datasets and smaller values of α , CG was found to exhibit superior performance. Consequently, it follows that if the size of the data set to be labelled is not substantial, then CG should be preferred as the solver. This is also the case because, for datasets of a smaller scale, it is possible to select a lower value of α , since it is unnecessary to distribute information across a wide spectrum.

(a) Time of the solution phase for $\alpha = 0.6$. (b) Time of the solution phase for $\alpha = 0.99$.

Figure 6.3.6: Impact of n_{data} for EMNIST-Digits data.

6.4 Animals10

In this section, label spreading is applied to an image classification system dataset containing higher-resolution images. For this purpose, the Animals10 dataset [7] is utilized, which comprises 26,179 images of animals belonging to the following classes: dog, horse, elephant, butterfly, chicken, cow, sheep, squirrel, cat, and spider. The dataset is not evenly distributed with respect to the number of images per class. Additionally, the resolution and size of the images vary. Figure 6.4.1 illustrates three representative images of the data set, which encompass a range of classes and sizes.

Figure 6.4.1: Three sample images from the Animals10 dataset.

In order to apply label spreading to this image data, it is necessary to reduce the dimensions of the images. This is achieved by first using CLIP to uniformly reduce the dimensions of the images to a dimension of 512. The dimension is then further reduced to dimension 50 with the help of UMAP. When applying label spreading, the number of nearest neighbors was selected as 50. Subsequently, the value of α was identified for which the highest classification accuracy could be attained when five images per class were labeled. The results are illustrated in Figure 6.4.2. As can be observed, high classification accuracy values for this data set are already achieved for relatively small values of α . An accuracy of 98.62% can already be achieved with $\alpha = 0.001$ using FGMRES+AMG. In contrast, when using CG, an accuracy of only 80.53% could be achieved for this value of α . This once again indicates the superior performance of FGMRES+AMG as a solver in label spreading. Nevertheless, the maximum classification accuracy of 98.75% is achieved with $\alpha = 0.999$ and can be attained when employing CG or FGMRES+AMG. For this value of α , the time required for the label spreading algorithm for the Animals10 dataset can be found in Table 6.4.1. It should be noted that the time required to solve the linear system is only a few seconds when using the SciPy implementation of CG, but this time can be reduced to less than one second when using the CG or FGMRES+AMG implemented with the AmgX library. In this context, the CG solver implemented with the AmgX library is the most efficient, although it should be noted that the Animals10 dataset comprises a relatively small number of images in comparison to the EMNIST-Digits dataset. Consequently, it can be expected that the FGMRES+AMG solver will perform more effectively on the Animal10 dataset if a

greater quantity of data were available. The complete label spreading algorithm for the Animals10 dataset is completed in approximately six minutes.

Figure 6.4.2: Classification accuracy for the Animals10 dataset for different values of α .

Step:	CG (SciPy)	CG (AmgX)	FGMRES+AMG
Reduction	361.94s	361.94s	361.94s
NN-Search	349.98s	349.98s	349.98s
Setup	0.00s	0.00s	0.04s
Solve	3.23s	0.30s	0.58s
Setup+Solve	3.23s	0.30s	0.62s
Label spreading	353.22s	350.41s	350.78s

Table 6.4.1: The classification accuracy that could be achieved is 98.75% for $\alpha=0.999$. For the duration of the entire label spreading algorithm, the time to reduce the dimension is not included but considered to be preprocessing.

In order to comprehend the circumstances that permit the attaining of such elevated classification accuracy values with minimal values of α , the length of the shortest paths between two data points in the graph (X, E, W) was examined on a random subsample of 100 data points and compared with those from the EMNIST-Digits dataset, where high accuracies could only be achieved with high values of α . The length of a path in a

graph is defined as the number of edges between two distinct nodes in the graph. Figure 6.4.3 provides an illustration of the study.

Figure 6.4.3: Frequency of the length of the shortest paths between data points.

As illustrated, shorter paths are more prevalent in the Animals10 dataset than in the EMNIST-Digits dataset. In the Animals10 dataset, the majority of the shortest paths are in the range of two to eight edges, with the longest shortest path being 17 edges long. In contrast, in the EMNIST-Digits dataset, the majority of the shortest paths range from four to approximately 20 edges. The longest shortest path in this dataset is 39 edges long, which is significantly longer than in the Animals10 dataset. This could indicate that a lower spreading intensity α is necessary to disseminate information through the graph, given that the paths in the Animals10 dataset are considerably shorter than those in the EMNIST-Digits dataset. In the EMNIST-Digits dataset, a greater intensity of spreading is necessary to disseminate information, as longer paths must be traversed. This is because the information associated with a data point is distributed across the edges and weighted with α over each edge. In the case of a graph with only short paths, as exemplified by the Animals10 dataset, every data point can be reached with a relatively low value of α . In contrast, for graphs with long paths, such as the EMNIST-Digits dataset, a larger value of α is required to reach every data point. It is important to note that the datasets do differ in terms of size. The Animals10 dataset comprises 26,179 data points, while the EMNIST-Digits dataset contains 280,000 data points. Given that there are more data points in the EMNIST-Digits dataset, it is to be expected that longer shortest paths will be found in this dataset. This is because the number of data points leads to longer paths.

6.5 Probabilistic Label Spreading

In this section, experiments are conducted to analyze the performance of probabilistic label spreading. Unlike the application of label spreading on classification problems, where the linear system of equations is solved only once for each class, in probabilistic label spreading the linear system of equations must be solved for each conducted crowdsourcing experiment. Consequently, in this setting, it is of great importance to use an efficient solver. To conduct experiments, the EMNIST-Digits data set was utilized once more, containing 280,000 images. The data was once again reduced to dimension 50 by using UMAP, and the affinity matrix was constructed by using 50 nearest neighbors. Probabilistic labels for the data were obtained through the use of a small neural network. This network consisted of an input layer with 785 neurons, a dense hidden layer with 128 neurons, and a rectified linear unit (RELU) activation function. The output layer had $n_{classes}$ number of neurons, with the softmax activation function. This function transforms the outputs into probabilistic values for belonging to each class. The softmax output serves as the probabilistic labels p^* . The objective of probabilistic labeling is to minimize the difference between the true probability distributions p^* and the probabilistic distributions derived from crowdsourcing experiments \hat{p} for each data point. The initial probability distribution for each data point is assumed to be uniform. It is important to note that the true probabilistic labels p^* are unknown in reality; however, they are set to be the softmax outcome of our neural network in this study. Consequently, the difference between the probability distributions can be quantified as the root mean squared error between the probabilities across all classes and over all data points

$$L^2(p^*, \hat{p}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{data} \cdot c} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{data}} \sum_{j=1}^c (p_{i,j}^* - \hat{p}_{i,j})^2}.$$

The objective of this study is to determine the number of human-conducted crowdsourcing experiments required to achieve an L^2 -error of less than 10%. In order to ascertain the efficacy of probabilistic label spreading, this approach is evaluated for varying values of α . The case where $\alpha = 0$ is also considered, which represents the absence of label spreading, but rather, only the conduction of crowdsourcing experiments. The following number of crowdsourcing experiments were examined: 0.01%, 0.1%, 1%, 10%, 100%, 200% of the number of data points in the dataset, in addition to values between these points and up to a maximum of 700,000 experiments and starting with 0 experiments. The corresponding L^2 -error achieved with a certain number of experiments was then analyzed. Furthermore, two experimental designs are considered in the present study. The first is a crowdsourcing experiment randomly selected from all data points, and the second is a parallel study in which an equal number of experiments are conducted for each class. Firstly, the experimental setup is considered, wherein experiments are randomly selected from all data points. This is depicted in Figure 6.5.1. It can be observed that as the value of α increases, the number of required crowdsourcing

experiments decreases, thereby achieving a reduction of 10% in the L^2 -error with the smallest possible number of crowdsourcing experiments when $\alpha = 0.999$. When this result is compared to a scenario in which no spreading is employed, i.e., $\alpha = 0$, it can be observed that the number of required human-conducted crowdsourcing experiments can be reduced from 1,000,000 to only 100. This represents a significant achievement, as the conduct of 1,000,000 crowdsourcing experiments is both costly and time-consuming. Furthermore, the same improvement in error can be achieved by conducting only 100 crowdsourcing experiments and then applying probabilistic label spreading, which is both more cost-effective and faster. In the subsequent phase of the experiment, we

Figure 6.5.1: The reduction in the L^2 -error when different values of α are employed in probabilistic label spreading, when the sampling is conducted randomly, is demonstrated.

examine the impact of randomly selecting experiments in a way that ensures an equal number of experiments are conducted within each class. The results of this experiment are depicted in Figure 6.5.2. It appears that conducting an equal number of experiments per class has no impact when no spreading is employed. However, when spreading is applied, there is an impact. For α is equal to 0.9 and 0.6, more fluctuations in the course of the graph can be observed. Additionally, the α value for the smallest possible number of crowdsourcing experiments is now 0.99, rather than 0.999, which results in a lower intensity of spreading.

A particularly encouraging outcome is that the minimum number of crowdsourcing experiments can be reduced to 20 when setting $\alpha = 0.99$, which is even lower than the number required when experiments are conducted randomly on the data without

consideration of the distribution across classes. However, in practice, it may not be feasible to label the same instances of data for each class.

Figure 6.5.2: The reduction in the L^2 -error when different values of α are employed in probabilistic label spreading, when the sampling is conducted randomly and in a balanced manner with respect to the classes, is demonstrated.

To further investigate the potential for reducing the L^2 -error, an additional experiment was conducted. In this experiment, the number of crowdsourcing experiments conducted without the use of probabilistic label spreading was increased from the initial 50 up to one million. In addition, the number of experiments conducted with probabilistic label spreading was increased from the initial 50 to a maximum of 100 % of the number of data points in the EMNIST-Digits dataset, which is 280,000. It is crucial to acknowledge that the linear system must be solved a total of n_{sample} times. Consequently, a considerable number of crowdsourcing experiments when probabilistic label spreading is employed will result in lengthy runtimes. For instance, when 28,000 crowdsourcing experiments are conducted, the time to solve the linear system 28,000 times takes 3,7 hours when probabilistic label spreading is employed with $\alpha = 0.999$.

It was found that the L^2 -error exhibited a downward trend, indicating the potential for further reduction. A comparison was conducted to ascertain the extent to which the L^2 -error is reduced when not spreading, as opposed to spreading with an intensity of $\alpha = 0.999$ and $\alpha = 0.9$. The results of the investigations are presented in Figure 6.5.3. The smallest L^2 -error achieved using probabilistic label spreading with $\alpha = 0.999$ is 9.1%. It can be observed that after 100 crowdsourcing experiments, the decline of the L^2 -error almost stagnates. If probabilistic label spreading is used with $\alpha = 0.9$, the

smallest achieved L^2 -error is 7.7%. Additionally, for this value of α , after 100 conducted crowdsourcing experiments, the L^2 -error also declines at a slower but more pronounced rate than when $\alpha = 0.999$ is employed. When no spreading is applied, a reduction to 8.1% can be achieved if 840,000 experiments are conducted. However, if the number of experiments is further increased to 1 million, no significant decrease in the L^2 -error can be observed. This can be interpreted as follows: In the absence of probabilistic label spreading, the following applies to $n_{samples}$. If $n_{samples} \rightarrow \infty$, the estimated labels from crowdsourcing experiments converge to the true labels. Consequently, the L^2 -error converges to zero. However, this is not yet the case here, as it appears that insufficient experiments have been conducted. Nevertheless, future research should investigate the implications of an expanded series of crowdsourcing experiments. In the event that probabilistic label spreading is employed, the outcomes may be interpreted as follows: When a high spreading intensity α is employed, a substantial amount of information is disseminated throughout the graph (X, E, W) . Consequently, even with a limited number of crowdsourcing experiments, a considerable amount of information is disseminated. Nevertheless, as the number of crowdsourcing experiments is increased, the ratio of new relevant information for each data point is not as significant, resulting in a stagnating decline in the L^2 -error. This issue can be circumvented by selecting a lower spreading intensity when the stagnation of the L^2 -error begins when conducting more crowdsourcing experiments. The newly acquired information from a new crowdsourcing experiment would then be employed in a more selective manner, thereby reducing the L^2 -error more expeditiously by limiting the information flow of data points to those data points that are proximal, thus ensuring the utilization of the most pertinent information.

Figure 6.5.3: A comparison of the reduction in the L^2 -error for probabilistic label spreading versus no spreading is conducted when multiple crowdsourcing experiments were performed.

Time Measurements of Probabilistic Label Spreading

6.5.1

The final experiments to be presented are those examining the time required for probabilistic label spreading when using different solvers. The resulting time measurements are presented where $\alpha = 0.999$ and $n_{samples} = 100$, when sampling randomly across all data points. As illustrated in Figure 6.5.1, 100 is the minimum number of crowdsourcing experiments that must be conducted to achieve a reduction of the L^2 -error to 10%. The following steps of probabilistic label spreading are presented with time measurements. It should be noted that step which involves reducing the dimensionality of the data, is once again classified as a preprocessing step.

1. **NN-Search:** The calculation of the nearest neighbors of each data point. For the nearest neighbors search, the *NearestNeighbors* class from the *scikit-learn* library is utilized, configured to use the *ball tree* algorithm [19].
2. **Setup:** The setup phase for AmgX-based solvers, which involves the construction of coarser levels.
3. **Solve:** The solution phase, including the time required to solve the linear system of equations $n_{samples}$ times and to update the amount of information each data point has received from a sample.
4. **Setup+Solve:** The setup and solution phases, considered together, including the timing of data transmission to the GPU and subsequent reloading when using AmgX-based solvers.
5. **Probabilistic label spreading:** The entire approach to probabilistic label spreading, including the calculation of the L^2 -error

Step:	CG (AmgX)	FGMRES+AMG
Reduction	611.26s	611.26s
NN-Search	134.91s	134.91s
Setup	0.00s	0.62s
Solve	68.63s	37.12s
Setup+Solve	69.39s	38.65s
Probabilistic label spreading	264.31s	233.70s

Table 6.5.1: Time measurements for reducing the L^2 -error in probabilistic label spreading for the EMNIST-Digits dataset. The data was reduced with UMAP, and $\alpha = 0.999$.

Table 6.5.1 depicts the time measurements of probabilistic label spreading. The steps to reduce the dimensionality of the data and the time calculate the nearest neighbors are

identical to those employed in label spreading for the classification task. It is noteworthy that the time required for the reduction of data and the calculation of nearest neighbors is less critical than that for the solution phase. This is because these steps are executed only once. The solution phase, on the other hand, depends on $n_{samples}$ and increases with $n_{samples}$. Additionally, the time required for the setup phase of the matrix is identical to that required for label spreading in classification, as the matrix is identical in both cases. The time required for the solution phase is significantly reduced when FGMRES+AMG is employed as the solver, in comparison to when CG is utilized. The 100-times solve of the linear system of equations necessitates less than 40 seconds when FGMRES+AMG is employed. This results in the time required for the probabilistic label spreading algorithm being approximately four minutes.

7

Conclusion and Outlook

As demonstrated in the experimental section, the incorporation of the AmgX library for solvers for the linear system of equations arising in label spreading rendered label spreading a computationally efficient method for the automated labeling of a dataset when a small amount of data is labeled by humans. Consequently, the creation of large datasets has become feasible by eliminating the necessity of manual labeling of the whole dataset. Instead, a small subset of data can be designated for labeling, and label spreading, which has been demonstrated to result in high classification accuracy and a rapid approach, can be employed. Furthermore, label spreading in the application of probabilistic data was enhanced by the incorporation of an efficient solver. It was demonstrated that the use of probabilistic label spreading could result in the significant reduction of the number of human-conducted crowdsourcing experiments required, thus saving a considerable amount of time and resources. It was shown that by utilising less information gained from human-conducted crowdsourcing experiments but sharing this information across the dataset, it was possible to reduce the error in a manner similar to that achieved when conducting a significantly larger number of crowdsourcing experiments. It is crucial to acknowledge that the epistemic uncertainty inherent in probabilistic labels is diminished by probabilistic label spreading, which is a consequence of the acquisition of additional information.

Moreover, it was demonstrated that the utilization of an efficient solver is a prerequisite for the implementation of label spreading for large datasets as an efficacious and practical methodology. The direct solution to a linear system of equations in label spreading is not feasible due to its intractability, while the use of iterative methods, implemented with SciPy, also results in a considerable delay. The utilization of solvers from the AmgX library led to a significant enhancement, with the FGMRES+AMG method exhibiting the most optimal performance for label spreading on large datasets. Moreover, it must be acknowledged that additional reductions in computation time can be attained by limiting the precision of the solve with FGMRES+AMG, for instance, to 10^{-1} , as evidenced by the observation that comparable classification accuracy can be achieved when solving with high precision of 10^{-12} . This research presented the optimal choice of smoother and number of coarse levels for AMG, which are the Gauß-Seidel smoother and five coarse levels, when applied to label spreading. The aforementioned choices were subsequently employed during the configuration of the FGMRES+AMG solver. Furthermore, this work included a comprehensive examination of the impact of label spreading parameters on the solution for the linear system of equations in label spreading. It was demonstrated that an increase in the value of the spreading intensity parameter α results in an increase in the condition number of the linear system of equations,

thereby necessitating greater computational resources. When using label spreading with large values of α , the FGMRES+AMG solver is not as sensitive as the CG solver to the increasing condition number. Additionally, the number of nearest neighbors was found to influence the computational efficiency, with an increasing number resulting in a proportional increase in computational work. When considering the label spreading parameters for which the highest accuracy in label spreading could be achieved, it was observed that FGMRES+AMG yielded the most optimal performance. However, the most significant finding of this study was that the solver of the linear system of equations exerts a significant influence on the accuracy that can be attained. It was demonstrated that by employing FGMRES+AMG, higher classification accuracies could be obtained in a shorter time and with a smaller number of iterations than if CG was utilized. The results indicate that the FGMRES+AMG solver is the optimal choice for label spreading applications. Therefore, its use should be prioritized over CG. Furthermore, it was found that the label spreading method is robust to datasets of varying size and resolution. It was demonstrated that high classification accuracies were achievable for all datasets used, even if the dimension of the data had to be reduced beforehand. Additionally, the different solvers behaved similarly on all datasets. Therefore, it can be concluded that as long as the data can be well clustered into their classes, label spreading is a robust method.

When contemplating future endeavors in the domain of efficient label spreading and efficient probabilistic label spreading for large datasets, it was demonstrated that there is potential for reducing the computation time required for calculating the nearest neighbors for constructing the affinity matrix. This observation opens avenues for exploring alternative approaches and implementations. An alternative approach would be to construct the graph in a different way, for instance by determining the edges and edge weights in a different manner. One possible modification would be to not construct the edges based on the nearest neighbors, but rather to connect one data point to all others within a certain radius. In addition, the edge weights could be selected differently if alternative similarity measures were to be examined. Moreover, a more comprehensive analysis of the dimensionality reduction method and its impact on the solver could be conducted, as the dimensionality reduction is a crucial step in making label spreading applicable to high-dimensional data and in obtaining accurate accuracy results. Additionally, a study could be conducted to identify which data points require labeling in order to achieve greater accuracy. A targeted selection of the data points to be labeled could result in more efficient label spreading. One could attempt to ascertain whether the coarsest grid utilized in multigrid methods could provide insight into this matter. Moreover, an alternative stopping criterion for algebraic multigrid could be considered to enhance the computation time. This criterion would involve monitoring the predicted classification in label spreading after each iteration and halting the process when there is no further change in the predicted classification for a number of iterations. To further extend the applicability of label spreading, it is essential to test the label spreading approach on a diverse array of datasets. Furthermore, the applicability of label spreading may be extended to other machine learning tasks that require large amounts of labeled data, such as semantic segmentation and object detection.

References

- [1] X. Bai and E. R. Hancock. Heat kernels, manifolds and graph embedding. In *Structural, Syntactic, and Statistical Pattern Recognition: Joint IAPR International Workshops, SSPR 2004 and SPR 2004, Lisbon, Portugal, August 18-20, 2004. Proceedings*, pages 198–206. Springer, 2004.
- [2] D. Bertaccini and F. Durastante. *Iterative methods and preconditioning for large and sparse linear systems with applications*. Chapman and Hall/CRC, 2018.
- [3] B. M. Böddecker. *Probabilistic Label Spreading for Reliable Semi-Automated Image Labeling*. 2024.
- [4] O. Chapelle, B. Scholkopf, and A. Zien. Semi-supervised learning. 2006. *Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press View Article*, 2, 2006.
- [5] F. R. Chung. *Spectral graph theory*, volume 92. American Mathematical Soc., 1997.
- [6] G. Cohen, S. Afshar, J. Tapson, and A. van Schaik. EMNIST: an extension of MNIST to handwritten letters. *CoRR*, abs/1702.05373, 2017. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/1702.05373>.
- [7] A. Corrado. Animals10 dataset. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/alessiocorrado99/animals10>, 2019. Dataset version 2.
- [8] H. De Sterck, U. M. Yang, and J. J. Heys. Reducing complexity in parallel algebraic multigrid preconditioners. *SIAM Journal on Matrix Analysis and Applications*, 27(4):1019–1039, 2006.
- [9] H. De Sterck, R. D. Falgout, J. W. Nolting, and U. M. Yang. Distance-two interpolation for parallel algebraic multigrid. *Numerical Linear Algebra with Applications*, 15(2-3):115–139, 2008.
- [10] P. Grother. Nist special database 19 handprinted forms and characters database. 1995. URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:59785963>.
- [11] A. Iscen, G. Tolia, Y. Avrithis, and O. Chum. Label propagation for deep semi-supervised learning. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 5070–5079, 2019.
- [12] G. James, D. Witten, T. Hastie, and R. Tibshirani. *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: with Applications in R*. Springer, 2013. URL <https://faculty.marshall.usc.edu/gareth-james/ISL/>.
- [13] A. Jung. *Machine learning: the basics*. Springer Nature, 2022.

- [14] Y. LeCun, C. Cortes, and C. Burges. Mnist handwritten digit database. *ATT Labs [Online]*. Available: <http://yann.lecun.com/exdb/mnist>, 2, 2010.
- [15] L. McInnes, J. Healy, and J. Melville. Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction, 2020.
- [16] K. P. Murphy. *Probabilistic Machine Learning: An introduction*. MIT Press, 2022. URL probml.ai.
- [17] NVIDIA Corporation. AMGx: An algorithmic multigrid preconditioner for scalable linear system solvers. <https://developer.nvidia.com/amgx>, Year of the version you are referring to. Accessed: February 16, 2026.
- [18] Y. Ouali, C. Hudelot, and M. Tami. An overview of deep semi-supervised learning, 2020.
- [19] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and É. Duchesnay. Scikit-learn: Machine learning in python. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12:2825–2830, 2011.
- [20] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg, J. Vanderplas, A. Passos, D. Cournapeau, M. Brucher, M. Perrot, and E. Duchesnay. Generating two interleaving half circles. https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.datasets.make_moons.html, 2011. Accessed: February 16, 2026.
- [21] P. Peng, R. C.-W. Wong, and P. S. Yu. Learning on probabilistic labels. In *Proceedings of the 2014 SIAM International Conference on Data Mining*, pages 307–315. SIAM, 2014.
- [22] A. Radford, J. W. Kim, C. Hallacy, A. Ramesh, G. Goh, S. Agarwal, G. Sastry, A. Askell, P. Mishkin, J. Clark, G. Krueger, and I. Sutskever. Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. *CoRR*, abs/2103.00020, 2021. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.00020>.
- [23] Y. Saad. *Iterative methods for sparse linear systems*. SIAM, 2003.
- [24] U. Shaham, K. Stanton, H. Li, B. Nadler, R. Basri, and Y. Kluger. Spectralnet: Spectral clustering using deep neural networks, 2018.
- [25] A. J. Smola and R. Kondor. Kernels and regularization on graphs. In *Learning Theory and Kernel Machines: 16th Annual Conference on Learning Theory and 7th Kernel Workshop, COLT/Kernel 2003, Washington, DC, USA, August 24-27, 2003. Proceedings*, pages 144–158. Springer, 2003.
- [26] A. Srinath. *pyamgx - GPU Accelerated Multigrid Library for Python*, 2018. URL <https://github.com/shwina/pyamgx>. Accessed: 2024-05-15.

- [27] K. Stüben et al. An introduction to algebraic multigrid. *Multigrid*, pages 413–532, 2001.
- [28] J. B. Tenenbaum, V. d. Silva, and J. C. Langford. A global geometric framework for nonlinear dimensionality reduction. *science*, 290(5500):2319–2323, 2000.
- [29] L. N. Trefethen and D. Bau. *Numerical Linear Algebra*. SIAM, 1997. ISBN 0898713617.
- [30] U. Trottenberg, C. W. Oosterlee, and A. Schuller. *Multigrid*. Elsevier, 2000.
- [31] P. Virtanen, R. Gommers, T. E. Oliphant, M. Haberland, T. Reddy, D. Cournapeau, E. Burovski, P. Peterson, W. Weckesser, J. Bright, et al. Scipy 1.0: fundamental algorithms for scientific computing in python. *Nature Methods*, 17(3):261–272, 2020.
- [32] P. Zaspel. Introduction to scientific computing; lecture notes.
- [33] D. Zhou, O. Bousquet, T. Lal, J. Weston, and B. Schölkopf. Learning with local and global consistency. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 16, 2003.